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Domestic Abuse links to Suicide:

Rapid Review, Fieldwork, and Quantitative Analysis Report

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Report Overview

The link between domestic abuse and suicide remains significantly under-researched. However, as awareness of this issue grows, the connection is becoming increasingly evident. This has been clearly demonstrated in the latest Domestic Homicides and Suspected Victim Suicides Report (2022-2023), which revealed that suspected suicide, for the first time, has been reported as the leading cause of death, emphasizing the need for a greater understanding of this issue and development of targeted interventions.

The following report presents research examining the relationship between domestic abuse and suicide, drawing on current literature, lived experiences, and data from police and coroners. The primary aim of the research is to develop further understanding of the connection between domestic abuse, suicide, and suicidal ideation.

Findings from the Rapid Evidence Review provide a comprehensive overview of existing knowledge on the link between domestic abuse and suicide. Building on this, a conceptual framework was developed to guide the qualitative fieldwork, which explores the issue from a lived experience perspective. The outcomes of this fieldwork, combined with the conceptual framework, propose a theoretical model that offers insights into the potential mechanisms and underlying reasons behind the impact of various factors that contribute to thoughts of suicide. These findings are further contextualized through a quantitative evaluation, which highlights the scale, prevalence, and complexities of this issue.

Results inform recommendations for practice and further research, these include:

The development and piloting of new assessment tool which can assist frontline workers in police and healthcare settings to identify those at risk of suicide following domestic abuse.

Guidance is developed for police and health services to introduce and maintain a domestic abuse suicide prevention support pathway.

Victim's contact with services, other than police and healthcare, are explored in relation to this topic, including family courts, children's social care, and community sector services.

More nuanced research is conducted to explore the trajectory from abuse to suicidality.

Quantitative and qualitative research is conducted to gain greater understanding of the high incidence of suicide amongst perpetrators of domestic abuse.

Executive Summary

Introduction

The UK police received, on average, over 100 domestic abuse-related calls an hour in 2014/15, which represents 10% of all recorded crime (HMIC, 2015). To date, very little systematic data have been gathered on the relationship between domestic abuse and victim suicide in the UK. In one of the first projects of its kind, the police and government in England and Wales established the Domestic Homicides Project to collect, review, and share quick-time learning from all police-recorded domestic homicides and suspected suicides of individuals with a history of domestic abuse victimisation nationally. During Covid-19 and attendant restrictions, the Project commissioned the Vulnerability Knowledge and Practice Programme, which published the report "Domestic Homicides and Suspected Victim Suicides During the Covid-19 Pandemic 2020-2021" (hereafter, the VKPP Report). Unexplained or suspicious deaths, and suspected suicides of individuals with a known history of domestic abuse, were included in the VKPP Report definition to allow for capturing as wide a range of deaths following domestic abuse as possible. Key findings from the VKPP reports informed this report and are as follows:

The most recent VKPP Report to date (2022-2023) revealed that there were 242 deaths in the 12 months from April 2022 to 31 March 2023 reported by the police in England and Wales. The largest proportion of deaths in this period were suspected victim suicides (93). This was an increase by a third compared to the previous year and the first time in which suspected suicide has surpassed deaths by intimate partner violence (80). It can be suggested that this significant increase is due to an increased awareness of suicide and reporting, however, with available evidence an empirical increase cannot be ruled out.

Since the initial 2020-2021 VKPP report, a significant majority of the recorded 216 deaths by suspected suicide have been female (80%). Despite this, across the three years of VKPP data collection there has been a consistent increase in male suspected suicide, from 12% in year one to 26% in year three. Overall, the majority deaths by suicide recorded by VKPP are recorded to have been aged between 22 and 44 (57%), though this type of death in the 45-54 age bracket has been increasing year on year (15% in year 2, 27% in year 3).

The most common cause of death in suspected victim suicides was hanging, with 63% of victims dying this way in the latest report. This appears consistent with wider data relating to suicide, hanging, strangulation, and suffocation as the most common method of suicide in England and Wales for both men and women.

Over the course of the three-year VKPP reporting, the data shows a slightly smaller percentage of White victims and suspects, and a higher percentage of victims and suspects from minority ethnic backgrounds compared to the general population. This was especially the case for victims and suspects of Black ethnicity. It has been found in other work by the VKPP that victims of Black ethnicity are less inclined to report domestic abuse to the police but are equally likely to reach out to independent advocates for help. This makes clear the need for officers to build cultural competence to better support these communities.

In the most recent year of the report, 38% of perpetrators in cases of suspected suicide were previously known to the police as victims of domestic abuse. This 38% had an equal split between male and female cases. However, in cases where a male perpetrator was also known as a victim, they were more often identified as the primary perpetrator in the overall case.

Present Project

Drawing on the VKPP report and other literature as a starting point, the present project aimed to further understand the relationships between:

- Domestic abuse and individuals dying by suicide;
- Sociodemographic characteristics and domestic abuse-related suicide;
- Different forms of domestic abuse and victims dying by suicide; and
- Forced Marriage/Honour Based Violence (FM/HBV) and domestic abuse-related suicide.

To achieve this, the following three strands of research were conducted:

- 1** Rapid evidence review. The review examined the long- and short-term causes, drivers and aggravating factors of domestic abuse (e.g., physical, emotional, psychological, financial) related suicide, to deliver a strong evidence base for identifying risk factors.
- 2** Fieldwork. A qualitative study with domestic abuse victims was conducted to better understand the relationship between domestic abuse and risk factors for suicide.
- 3** Quantitative Analysis. A quantitative study of domestic abuse incidents and suicide to better understand how the incidence of suicide differs amongst the victims and perpetrators of domestic violence, and how this is correlated with its form.

Rapid Evidence Review

A rapid evidence review was conducted using a PICO framework to summarize the current literature regarding suicide following domestic abuse.

Findings from this review indicated that coercion and control is linked with suicide. It involves emotional and psychological manipulation and abuse and is experienced by between 88-91% of victims. Research suggests the life-threatening experience of nonfatal strangulation as a strong contributor to victim suicidality. It may be that nonfatal strangulation is an effective facilitator of coercion and control. An abuse which appears to be highly correlated with victim suicide is sexual assault/rape. Further, financial abuse, another form of coercion and control, was experienced by a third of victims and contributed to their suicidality.

The review indicated that victim depression and PTSD is linked to severity of the abuse and suicide. Non-fatal attempted suicide is co-morbid with depression for 20% of the domestic abuse victims. PTSD and depression are positively correlated with repetition of abuse, multiple concurrent forms of abuse, and the victim enduring multiple forms of abuse, including physical abuse, sexual abuse, and rape.

The four key contributors to suicidality are: physical and emotional/psychological pain, hopelessness (including powerlessness/helplessness), lack of connectedness (disrupted relationships and isolation), and suicide capability (i.e., the means to take one's own life) Added to this has been 'burdensomeness', which is associated with self-hatred. There is a link between individuals having less self-compassion, feeling less belongingness, and experiencing a higher level of burdensomeness; these factors have been associated with increased depressive symptoms.

Substance use is associated with suicidality. Self-harm is also a predictor of suicide and shares common risk factors with suicidality.

Fieldwork

The principal fieldwork data were collected from 34 previous victims of domestic abuse and the secondary fieldwork data were collected from two families who had lost a family member to suicide where that family member had experienced domestic abuse.

All the participants in our research who attempted suicide were subjected to sexual assault/rape. They also experienced an average of 17 different forms of abuse. The link between these abuses and suicidality is explained in the literature by the fact that they cause depression and PTSD, and are commonly experienced co-morbidly. Unfortunately, we were not in a position to administer diagnostic questionnaires to establish whether the participants in our research had depression and/or PTSD. However, there is the potential that they did have one or both because many of their descriptions include the risk factors for depression and PTSD. These were sexual assault/rape, life threatening abuse, repetition of abuse, multiple concurrent abuses, inclusion in the multiple abuses of physical and abuse and sexual assault/rape.

We were able to establish feelings states consciously experienced by participants. According to the rapid evidence review, victims are more likely to attempt suicide if they experience hopelessness and despair. The participants in our field research similarly described feeling hopeless, feeling trapped by the perpetrator, and feeling that life was unbearable, with no chance of changing what was happening to them/their family – which we interpret as despair. Notably, in the field research, the three participants who did not have suicidal thoughts or attempt suicide did not feel that their life was unbearable.

The literature suggests that victims are more likely to attempt suicide if they experience feelings of panic, terror, and trauma, with the latter most often reported to stem from childhood experiences. All the participants in our field research described feeling extreme fear, which we would equate with the terms 'panic' and 'terror.' Unfortunately, we did not ask interviewees about prior traumatic events, such as adverse experiences in childhood; nevertheless, several of the participants in the field research did say that they experienced childhood trauma and/or that they had experienced domestic abuse in a previous relationship.

A last feeling state identified in the research literature as influencing victims to attempt suicide if they experienced it, is burdensomeness – specifically arising from disrupted relationships with self and others. All the participants in our research who had suicidal thoughts or attempted suicide described feeling that they were a burden and several of the mothers who attempted suicide described thinking that their children would be better off without them. The participants in our interview research who had suicidal thoughts or attempted suicide described feeling isolated and lonely, worthless, humiliated and that they were not as good as other people thought they were (e.g., feeling like a fraud). These feeling states are all functions of, and contributors to, disruption in a victim's relationship with others and with themselves – in conjunction with the shame and somatic distress which typically follows from abusive physical trauma.

Additionally, participants who attempted suicide appear to have been influenced by the participant's family pressuring her to stay with the perpetrator or to take him back when they knew about the abuse. Also, the participant having had one or more previous relationships in which she had experienced domestic abuse; and, critically, others not acting to help the participant when the participant knew that they had seen the signs of abuse and/or the victim had disclosed the abuse. The importance of this lay in the fact that help from outside of the abusive relationship and wider family was perceived by the participants as their last chance and when that help was not forthcoming, the participant's hope of escaping the abuse was extinguished. Many more of the participants who attempted suicide were in contact with the police than victims who had suicidal ideation or no suicidal thought/did not attempt suicide; and only just over a third of the participants who attempted suicide said that the police helped them whilst they were in the relationship. Similarly, participants' contact with health services seemed to have a significant influence on the participants. Almost all the participants who attempted suicide had contact with health services. Two-thirds were diagnosed with post-natal depression and were prescribed anti-depressants. Of the participants who were diagnosed with mental ill health due to the perpetrator's behaviour and influence, just over two-thirds attempted suicide.

With respect to suicide attempts, almost half of White British participants attempted suicide, compared to a third of the participants with 'other' ethnicities and only one British Pakistani participant. However, there are likely cross-cultural differences in participant's willingness to disclose suicidal ideation that could very well explain these ethnicity patterns.

In relation to whether being a mother precludes attempting suicide, this does not appear to be the case. In our research interviews, a third of participants who attempted suicide were caring for children at the time and said that they reached a point where they felt their children would be better off without them.

Finally, from the rapid review we understand that participants are more likely to attempt suicide if they try to cope with the impact of the abuse through drugs and alcohol or self-harm. In our research a high proportion of the participants who attempted suicide did use drugs and alcohol and/or self-harm as a way of coping. They also coped through eating in a disordered way. From the Rapid review we understand that eating in a disordered way is linked to burdensomeness via feelings of self-hatred. Whilst not long-term solutions, there were short-term coping strategies used by them participants in our research which were positive in the sense that they were not correlated with suicidal ideation/attempts. These included a strong reliance on religion, denial of the abuse and the victim having an ability to distract herself from the abuse and abusive circumstances.

Quantitative Analysis

The quantitative analysis compared data from West Midlands Police and coroners' offices regarding domestic abuse related suicide cases, this includes victims and perpetrators, with a control group of domestic abuse cases which did not include suicide over a 15-year period. Key findings include:

Suicide is significantly more prevalent in the domestic abuse (DA) population compared to the general population.

In both the general and domestic abuse populations, suicide is more common among men.

Perpetrators of domestic abuse have a higher likelihood of dying by suicide.

Among male suicide cases, 90% involved men as either the sole suspect or both a suspect and victim. Whereas in female suicide cases, around 40% were known as solely victims of domestic abuse.

The occurrence of death by suicide decreases as time passes since the last domestic abuse incident.

Individuals involved in a higher number of domestic abuse incidents are at greater risk of dying by suicide.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on our results, we recommend the creation and testing of an assessment tool that aims to identify the predictors of suicide by gathering information from the victim. Administration of the tool should include gathering information from whether they have experienced life-threatening abuse; sexual assault/rape, coercion and control; multiple abuses and repetition of abuse, as well as information about their feeling states, including feelings of despair, hopelessness and burdensomeness/ isolation/self-hatred. The tool should also take into account the effects of the abuse on the victim's self-identity, such as the number of relationships which have been disrupted or terminated. This should also elicit information about a victim's perceptions of/relationship with the police (and health services) and may assist in building trust; and any previous or childhood experiences which were trauma or terror-inducing, such as, some form of abuse, disaster (e.g., house fire), accident or medical procedure. Further information should be gathered about the victim's coping strategies, such as whether they are using self-harm and/or alcohol and drugs to cope.

We also recommend the development of guidelines for police forces and health services to introduce and maintain a domestic abuse victim suicide prevention/welfare pathway, with local statutory and VCS partners. The framework should contain the information in this report, and any other/up-dated information about how domestic abuse dismantles the victim's identity and the link with suicide translated into operational understanding and practice.

Additionally, we recommend that a small amount of additional funding is made available to explore the information collected in this research about the contact victims have had with services other than the police and health services (e.g. children's social care, schools, housing, immigration services, the Family courts and voluntary and community sector services). Moreover, more nuanced research needs to be undertaken to track the trajectory from abuse to suicidality and, in the process, to differentiate suicidal ideation from suicidality. The research should incorporate evaluation of any of the above pilot activities.

Finally, given that the quantitative analysis highlights the high rate of suicide amongst male perpetrators of domestic violence, further research is necessary to better understand this relationship and how it is affected by socio-economic factors, mental health, and substance use.

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Introduction

The research reported here forms three components of University of Birmingham's tripartite study into domestic abuse and suicide. The first component is a rapid evidence review seeking to summarise current knowledge about domestic abuse and any links to suicide. The review aimed to inform fieldwork with domestic abuse victims and families to understand their perspective on domestic abuse and whether/how it might in their experience have been linked to suicide. The fieldwork formed the second and primary component of the tripartite study, aiming to understand victims' experiences in their own words. Direct quotes have been used in this report to strengthen their voices. The third element of the overall study is a quantitative evaluation. The evaluation compares domestic abuse-related suicide cases with a control group of domestic abuse cases over the past 15 years held by the West Midlands police that did not involve suicide, including repeat victimisation, victimisation type, and vulnerability, and engagement with support services, such as mental and physical health, and substance use.

The ultimate goal for research such as this would be to contribute to improved practice in preventing death by suicide. Suicide not only cuts short the victim's life, it also has a significant negative impact on suicide-exposed people (whether or not they were related to the victim) who are themselves at risk for psychopathology and suicide (Jordan, 2001; Jordan and McIntosh, 2010). Improved practice could take the form of improved risk assessments and case pathways, and/or better single or multi-agency activity, and/or better staff training. Accordingly, this tri-partite study has focused on trying to identify key factors which might exacerbate or mitigate suicidal ideation and/or suicide attempts, such as, forms of abuse, coping mechanisms or service responses. Continued efforts in this area are important because to date the ability to predict death by suicide with any accuracy has remained low. Large (2018) summed this up as follows:

'Despite the widespread adoption of suicide risk assessment there are no published randomized trials demonstrating that risk assessment can guide any suicide-reducing interventions to the point of reducing the overall prevalence of suicide in the assessed group, and it remains to be seen if this evidence threshold can be achieved by any new suicide-predicting method.' (p202)

Research in Context

UK VAWG legislation, policy and policing

There has recently been increased government legislative and policy activity aimed at reducing the prevalence of crimes against women and girls. The Domestic Abuse Act¹ was passed in April 2021. Amongst other things, the Act introduced a statutory definition of domestic abuse, emphasising that domestic abuse is not just physical violence, but can also be emotional, controlling or coercive, and economic abuse. A national Tackling Violence Against Women and Girls (VAWG) Strategy² was launched in July 2021, and in March 2022 the government published the national Domestic Abuse Plan (England and Wales)³.

The Domestic Abuse Plan takes forward the findings from the Inspectorate's report setting out four areas of focus for service delivery: prioritising prevention, supporting victims, pursuing perpetrators, and developing a stronger service delivery system. A simplified version of the Plan is illustrated in Diagram 1.

Diagram 1: The national Tackling Domestic Abuse Plan (England and Wales)

Source: Adapted from the national Tackling Domestic Abuse Plan - Command paper 639 (accessible) (March 2022; updated 1 September 2022)

Additionally, an inspection from Her Majesty's Inspectorate of Constabulary and Fire & Rescue Services (HMICFRS)⁵ in mid-September 2021, concluded that while great improvements have been made in the policing response to VAWG over the last decade, these were not enough. The HMICFRS inspection also reported that there were significant inconsistencies in the service that police forces provide to women and girls across England and Wales. The inspectorate recommended a fundamental change in the police approach to crimes against women and girls, prioritising the response, and aiming for greater consistency and higher standards of service delivery.

One of the HMICFRS report's recommendations was for the NPCC to put in place a framework for force-level action plans, and work with chief constables to produce plans which would improve and their forces' response to violence against women and girls offences. The aim was to ensure policies, processes and practices are effective, actively monitored and managed, and meeting national standards. The NPCC published the framework in December 2021: the Policing violence against women and girls National framework for delivery: Year 1. It requires every police force to prioritise concentrated and determined action to achieve a common standard, culture and approach in preventing and responding to VAWG as part of any response to violent crime.

Included in this local response, and as part of the prevention part of the national Tackling Domestic Abuse Plan, should be a focus on preventing suicide linked to domestic abuse. In early 2020 the National Police Chiefs' Council and the College of Policing working with the Home-Office-funded National Policing Vulnerability Knowledge and Practice Programme (VKPP), produced a report: Domestic Homicides and Suspected Victim Suicides During the Covid-19 Pandemic 2020-2021 (Bates et al., 2021). The report was designed to share real-time learning from the police-recorded domestic homicides and suspected suicides of individuals with a history of domestic abuse victimisation over the pandemic period. The report acknowledged that unexplained or suspicious deaths, and suspected suicides of individuals with a known history of domestic abuse victimisation are not homicides, nevertheless they were included to take into account as wide a range of post-domestic abuse as possible.

Report Terminology and Presentation

Terminology

Domestic abuse: any incident or pattern of incidents of controlling, coercive or threatening behaviour, violence, or abuse between those aged 16 or over who are or have been intimate partners or family members regardless of gender or sexuality. This can encompass but is not limited to the following types of abuse: psychological, physical, sexual, financial, and emotional.

Honour-based violence: an incident or crime involving violence, threats of violence, intimidation coercion or abuse (including psychological, physical, sexual, financial or emotional abuse) which has or may have been chose to protect or defend the honour of an individual, family and/ or community for alleged or perceived breaches of the family and/or community's code of behaviour.

Suicidal ideation: there is no universally accepted consistent definition of suicidal ideation. the magnitude and characteristics of suicidal ideation fluctuate dramatically, it encompasses everything from fleeting wishes of falling asleep and never awakening to intensely disturbing preoccupations with self-annihilation fuelled by delusions.

Suicide and suicide attempt: suicide is when people harm themselves with the goal of ending their life, and they die as a result. A suicide attempt is when people harm themselves with the goal of ending their life, but they do not die (The National Institute for Mental Health).

In this report we have used phrases such as, "died by suicide", "death by suicide" and similar, to support the avoidance of negative connotations with these actions.

Our use of the term 'domestic abuse victim' in this report includes individuals who were experiencing domestic abuse at the time of reporting and/or who had experienced domestic abuse in the past.

Finally, we have used the terms 'feelings' and 'emotional and psychological impacts' in this report. 'Feeling' or 'feeling states' refers to the emotions which victims' are usually conscious of and can describe e.g., sadness. Whilst 'emotional and psychological impacts' refers to changes in mood and cognitive capability which can be outside of a victim's consciousness e.g., depression.

Presentation

We raise four issues in relation to presentation:

We subscribe to the view that in exploring complex circumstances, such as the link between domestic abuse and suicide, simplification loses the detail needed to understand and respond well. We have therefore tried to find a balance between providing as much of the detail as possible, in particular, by using the 'victims' voices' in quotes, and retaining 'readability' in this report.

To retain detail by including so many quotes has meant that we have needed to withhold the numbering of quotes to ensure participant confidentiality. For quality assurance purposes we have retained them in a securely stored version of this report.

We gathered a significant amount of information both about post-separation impacts on victims from stalking and the role of the Family courts/CAFCASS in facilitating this; and their role in introducing, maintaining or escalating suicidal ideation for the victims. We have not included that information in this report; but would very much like to add an addendum with the information.

We also gathered valuable information about victims' contact with services other than health and the police, children's social care, schools, housing, immigration services, the Family courts and voluntary and community sector services e.g., community and residential (Refuge) domestic abuse services and the Samaritans. We have not included that information in this report; but would like to add an addendum with the information.

Research Logic

Rapid review: to provide a context for the fieldwork, findings and discussion.

Conceptual framework: to investigate what the drivers of survivor suicide might be.

Fieldwork findings: answering the questions posed by the conceptual framework.

Theoretical framework: to explore why the drivers of survivor suicide might have the impact that they do.

Discussion: bringing together the findings from the conceptual framework and the theoretical framework with information from the rapid review (in particular Bates et al, 2021) and Aitken and Munro (2018).

Conclusion: taking a tentative position based on the discussion and making suggestions about potential next steps.

Rapid Evidence Review

Introduction

The link between domestic abuse and suicide is still largely under researched, however, as the literature on the topic continues to grow the connection is becoming more profound. A recent example of this includes the findings of the Domestic Homicides and Suspected Victim Suicides 2022-2023 Report, which recorded suspected victim suicide following domestic abuse as the leading cause of death for the first time since its creation.

Despite the significance of this issue only recently coming to light, the increased risk of suicidality and suicide among victims of abuse is not a new discovery and has been documented in other countries (Stark and Flitcraft, 1995; Cavanaugh et al., 2011; Sansone et al., 2007). In their large-scale study of domestic abuse and suicide in Australia, Maclsaac et al. (2016) found 42% of women who died by suicide had experienced domestic abuse, with 23% having been a victim of physical violence, 18% experiencing emotional and psychological violence, and 16% having been subjected to sexual abuse. Cavanaugh et al. (2011), undertook a secondary analysis of data from the Risk Assessment Validation (RAVE) Study (Roehl et al., 2005) in the USA and found that 20% of adult female victims of domestic abuse had been suicidal/attempted suicide during their lifetime.

Walby (2004) estimated that three women a week thought about escaping domestic abuse by taking their own lives and more than a third (33%) of all suicides were by women who had suffered domestic abuse. Taking a similar approach to Walby, Abraham (2005) positioned death by suicide as the only form of resistance the woman is able to engage in – the choice of whether or not to take her own life, because their partner controls everything else. According to Abraham, in these circumstances suicidal ideation reflects the extreme isolation and depression they experience. Ferraro (2006) also found that many women consider suicide as a way to stop the abuse because even separation will not necessarily stop the abuse; an alternative would be to murder the abusive partner.

In 2018 the Refuge and the University of Warwick published research by Aitken and Munro on domestic abuse and suicide based on data from victims using Refuge services. Findings were that 24% of victims had experienced suicidal ideation; 18% had planned how they would take their own lives and 3.1% had attempted suicide at least once. The findings indicated that victim suicidality was influenced by many of the specific forms of abuse listed in this review. Bates et al. (2021) noted that domestic abuse related suspected victim suicide and homicide in many ways have very similar risk profiles. In particular that cases of high-risk domestic abuse, often characterised by coercive control, might equally end in either a homicide or suspected victim suicide. The ideation highlights the loss of hope many women in abusive relationships experience.

Though domestic abuse related deaths by suicide are becoming more widely and are now included within Domestic Homicide Reviews, there is still a great need for improvement in the identification and consistency in the reporting of deaths by suicide (Dangar et al., 2023). More recent work on this topic further reflects on the evident and complex relationship between domestic abuse and suicide, calling for an improved holistic approach to victim support bringing together knowledge in both suicide prevention and responses to domestic abuse (Dangar et al., 2024). A more nuanced understanding of the impacts of domestic abuse is required especially within the criminal justice response, as the wider complexities of the issue such as suicidality, are not yet fully recognised and understood (Munro et al., 2024). This rapid evidence review aims to contribute to the growing body of research on domestic abuse and its links to suicide. By summarizing the current knowledge, the review will inform our fieldwork engagement with domestic abuse victims and families, as well as our quantitative analysis. Ultimately, the findings aim to deepen understanding and provide a basis for recommendations regarding improving responses to domestic abuse-related suicide.

Methodology

The literature search strategy was developed using the PICO framework designed to improve definition of the research question and to prompt for publication type and content. The framework is commonly used as guidance for conducting evidence reviews; as applied to this review it is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: PICO framework, domestic abuse and suicide

Population	Victims/victims of domestic abuse. Domestic abuse or intimate partner abuse/violence who die by suicide; suicide; attempted suicide and experience suicidal ideation.
Indicator	Dynamics and forms of domestic abuse e.g., physical, emotional, psychological, financial. Impact of domestic abuse on victims/victims e.g., physical symptoms and cognitive distortions; emotional dysregulation, anxious depressive and other states/behaviours and post post-traumatic stress disorder.
Comparator (control population)	Factors likely to inhibit suicide in victims/victims of domestic abuse/protective factors e.g., external factors and coping mechanisms.
Outcome (causation)	Factors likely to exacerbate suicide contemplation/attempts/risk factors. Compared to the impacts from domestic abuse on victims.

The search strategy was established with a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria to narrow the focus because it was anticipated that a large number of studies with potential relevance would be identified in the initial stages. The primary search focused on published academic literature which was English and reporting on research undertaken in Western societies with profiles broadly similar to the UK e.g., USA. However, due to the scarcity of research into the specifics of domestic abuse and suicide, a wider secondary search was made and articles added from other societies. The searches covered the period from January 2000 – December 2020; although, a few papers on seminal work from before that were also examined. Also included were very recent UK government evidence-based policy reports. In recognition of the maturity of the UK voluntary and community sector response to VAWG, grey literature from reputable organisations such as Women’s Aid, SafeLives and Refuge was also examined.

Findings: forms of abuse

Physical abuse

Aitken and Munro’s (2018) findings were that 74% of domestic abuse victims (women) had experienced physical abuse. They reported more than one form of abuse. The most common abuses were being pushed/pulled, punched, slapped, strangled and restrained. They were also kicked, injured with a weapon, suffocated, bitten, burned, stabbed and shot. For physical abuse the highest correlations with suicidality were in relation to physical abuse which was life threatening, including being strangled, kicked, or suffocated.

Non-fatal strangulation

Non-fatal strangulation is highlighted here because it is so prevalent, so dangerous and so gendered. Non-fatal strangulation usually leaves no external evidence, even where there is bruising and swelling, it often only becomes apparent days later; and the bruising may be difficult to detect on darker complexions (Baker & Sommers, 2008). Non-fatal strangulation is held to account for 17% of domestic abuse-related deaths in the UK (Long & Harvey, 2020). Non-fatal and fatal strangulation has been recognised as a gendered crime (Archer, 2000; Edwards, 2015; Bichard et al., 2021). Edwards (2015) reported that in England and Wales, over the previous three decades, this method of killing accounted for up to 37% of deaths of women by male partners. Bichard et al. reported that in 2018 that the second most common method of killing in female homicides was strangulation and asphyxiation, after stabbing (29% of women who died were killed by this method compared to only 3% of men). Glass et a. (2008) found that victims who are subjected to non-fatal strangulation were seven times more likely to be killed by their partners compared to victims who had not experienced non-fatal strangulation.

Thomas et al. (2014) reported that victims of non-fatal strangulation were clear that the assault was not a failed murder attempt, but a way for the perpetrator to exert power over them. However, despite other serious domestic abuse and intense fear, the victims were severely shocked by the assault because they were aware of how vulnerable they were to being killed. The victims reported largely failing in their efforts to extricate themselves from non-fatal strangulation and also, that their resistance resulted in an escalation of violence. Victims reported the impact of the assault to be so frightening that the strangulation did not need to be repeated (although it usually is) in order for the victim to be compliant and submissive. It is a powerful means of facilitating coercive control.

Several studies report that victims of non-fatal strangulation are at increased risk of developing significant physical and psychological problems immediately following the assault and weeks later. Victims of non-fatal strangulation are also at heightened risk of being killed by the perpetrator of the assault (Strack and McClane, 1999; Strack et al., 2001; Wilbur et al., 2001; Glass, et al., 2008; Foley, 2015). Strangulation can result in the loss of consciousness within seconds and brain death within minutes, following from the fact that pressure applied to the neck can damage blood vessels or the windpipe (airway) and/or cause clots. In addition to risk of death, it can cause brain damage or a stroke. Bichard et al. (2021) reported the impacts of non-fatal strangulation as follows: loss of consciousness, mild acquired brain injury, seizures, motor and speech disorders, paralysis, memory loss, increased aggression, compliance, and lack of help-seeking. Psychological distress in the immediate aftermath of the strangulation, reflects victims' fear that they were about to die (De Boos, 2019; Funk & Schuppel, 2003; Shields et al., 2010; Strack et al., 2001). Delayed psychological outcomes include: post-traumatic stress disorder, depression, anxiety, suicidality, nightmares and insomnia, generalised fear, powerlessness and vulnerability, shame, hypervigilance, dissociation, interpersonal difficulties, personality change, feelings of worthlessness (Bichard et al., 2021). Non-fatal strangulation is known to co-occur with sexual assault/rape (McQuown et al., 2016).

Bates et al's (2021) findings were that in the suspected victim suicide cases there was a history of non-fatal strangulation in approximately three-times more of the cases (28%) than in the cases where domestic abuse victim was killed by a partner (9%). Their findings included that coercive and controlling behaviour was much higher in the suspected victim suicide cases (56%) compared to the intimate partner homicide cases (30%) – and that non-fatal strangulation was present in two-fifths of the cases with coercive and controlling behaviour. Stalking has been recognised as a form of coercive control (Davis et al., 2000) and has also been found to be linked to non-fatal strangulation; 16.6% co-occurrence with stalking in research by Bendlin and Sheridan (2019).

Coercive control

Coercive control includes control of behaviour in and outside of the home – through actual or threatened physical abuse and emotional and psychological manipulation, financial control, isolation from friends and family, honour-based violence/forced marriage and reproductive coercion and control. Aitken and Munro (2018) found that isolation from family and friends and experiencing threats of harm with a weapon, threats to kill a family member, were correlated with suicidality. Bates, et al. (2021) concluded that coercion and control (together with previous experience of domestic abuse) was the most common risk factor for suspected victim suicides. Their finding was that victims of suspected suicide were three times more likely to have experienced coercive and controlling behaviour than victims of intimate partner homicide. Sato-DiLorenzo and Sharps (2007) describe victim symptoms related to coercive control within dangerous relationships: difficulty concentrating, memory loss, suicidal attempts, and weight gain.

Emotional and psychological manipulation/abuse

Safelives (2019) reported that 91% of victims had experienced a form of emotional and psychological manipulation/abuse, involving a pattern of intermittent grooming (constant communication and compliments) and abuse. It included 'silent treatment' (65%); suggestions the victim was mentally unstable (48%); shifting blame to the victim; presenting insults as a joke, presenting different versions of events; and verbal insults, humiliations, criticisms or putdowns (45%). These tactics are all known to cause psychological confusion prompting victims to doubt their own thinking and fear that they were 'losing their minds'. The Safelives report also notes the perpetrators' grooming of family and friends, behaving differently in public to private and, using their status or social standing to 'recruit allies'.

Aitken and Munro (2018) reported 87.87% of domestic abuse victims (women) having experienced emotional and psychological manipulation/abuse. A majority of victims reported being subjected to control and intimidation, followed by being subjected to isolation and threats of harm. The latter included a significant level of threats to family members and pets.

Financial abuse

Financial abuse occurs when a victim's current and future actions and their freedom of choice is curtailed and controlled by their partner using or misusing money. It can include using credit cards without permission, appropriating a victim's benefits, preventing her from accessing her own bank account, building up debt in her name and gambling with family assets (Sharp, 2008).

Aitken and Munro (2018) found that approximately a third of the victims experienced financial abuse, with just over a quarter reporting the perpetrator controlling the family finances. Furthermore, any report of financial abuse appeared to significantly increase the likelihood of suicidality. Economic abuse extends financial abuse to include restricting access to essential resources and denying a victim the means to improve her economic status e.g., through employment, education or training (Women's Aid, undated).

So called honour-based violence (HBV)

Aitken and Munro (2018) reported a correlation with suicidality amongst domestic abuse victims who described so-called 'honour' based violence. The proportion of victims who experienced honour-based violence was 4.1% and more than half of these clients (56.5%) were from South Asian backgrounds, representing 22.7% of all South Asian victims in the sample. These percentages are low, however, Annually, around 1,800 incidents are reported to the police in England and Wales (HMIC, 2015). Bates (2017) divided honour-based violence cases into three typologies: in Type I the sole perpetrator was a current or ex-intimate partner (as in other domestic abuse cases); in Type II the perpetrator was one or more of the victim's birth-family members, generally their birth family; and in Type III in a current or ex-intimate partner perpetrator, and in addition one or more of the victim's family members – most commonly their in-laws. Bates found that in types I and II the victim was at higher risk of harm – respectively 66% and 47%, compared to Type III which was 52% (as measured by SafeLives Insights data).

Reproductive coercion and abuse

Tarzia and Hegarty (2021) define reproductive coercion and abuse includes any deliberate attempt to influence or control a woman's reproductive autonomy, for the purpose of either preventing or promoting pregnancy. They argue that lack of a clear definition has prevented the establishment of a robust evidence base and that there is poor understanding of the way in which it interacts with domestic abuse and sexual violence. It is typically perpetrated against women by a male intimate partner (Grace et al., 2018), although other family members can also be participants or instigators (Silverman, 2019).

Reproductive coercion and control are currently recognised in three main forms: pregnancy coercion (where a woman is forced to become pregnant against her will); contraceptive sabotage; and controlling the outcome of a pregnancy (forcing a woman to terminate or continue a pregnancy against her will) (Grace et al., 2018). Aitken and Munro (2018) reported a small number of enforced terminations. A growing body of current research suggests associations between other forms of domestic abuse coercion and control and reproductive coercion and abuse (Silverman, 2019; Clark et al., 2014; Northridge et al., 2017; Samankasikorn et al., 2018), unwanted pregnancies (Grace et al., 2018), poor mental health (McCauley et al., 2014), decreased contraceptive self-efficacy (Gee et al., 2009; Katz et al., 2017) and increased risk of sexually transmitted infections (Kazmerski et al., 2015).

Sexual abuse

Aitken and Munro (2018) found that 30% of women said that they had been sexually abused. The most common form of abuse reported was forced vaginal intercourse i.e., rape. The victims said that it was one element of several ongoing forms of abuse they were subjected to. Women who experience sexual abuse are at risk for suicidal ideation or death by suicide (Coker, et al., 2002; Cavanaugh et al., 2011).

Findings: Emotional and psychological impacts

Psychological distress and injury

Forbes et al. (2014) found that the emotional and psychological distress of domestic abuse victims was almost four times higher than women in the general population (using a range of mental health measures). Aitken and Munro (2018) found strong evidence for psychological distress or injury across all of the 3,500 victim case records they sampled. Of these 86% met or surpassed the threshold for clinical concern on the Refugee's measure of psychological distress (CORE-10) and 83% of victims confirmed feeling despairing and hopeless. Within the suicidal group 49% scored in the severe range of psychological distress. Aitken and Munro's conclusion was that victims' feelings of despair or hopelessness; and experiencing panic, terror or past trauma were the most highly correlated with suicidality. Support for the contribution of the latter experiences comes from Pilowsky et al. (2006), who found that individuals with panic disorder were twice as likely to present with suicidal ideation, as those without panic disorder.

Mental ill health: depression, anxiety, PTSD, and C-PTSD

Pilowsky et al. (2006) found that individuals with depression were seven times more likely to experience suicidal ideation, as those without depression. For domestic abuse victims (women), Ferrari et al. (2016) reported that the proportion with symptoms of depression in their sample was double that of women in UK general practice; for symptoms of anxiety, this proportion is three times as large. Furthermore, they noted that these findings were consistent with those for women who were domestic abuse victims in the USA (Bell & Goodman, 2001; Becker et al., 2010) and Hong Kong (Sullivan et al., 1992). Chandan et al. (2019) found that female domestic abuse victims had double the risk of developing anxiety, and three times the risk of developing depression than women who had not experienced domestic abuse.

Aitken and Munro (2018) found that 86% of the victims in their research who were suicidal group reported feeling depressed. Sato-DiLorenzo and Sharps (2007) surveying women in domestic abuse shelters in the USA reported that anxiety and depression were linked to the level of seriousness of the abuse the victims had experienced. Devries et al. (2013) reviewing pre-2013 longitudinal studies also reported that experience of domestic abuse increases the likelihood of depressive symptoms and attempts of suicide among women.

Trevillion et al's (2012) systematic review of epidemiological studies of diagnosed mental illness found that post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) was higher for women who were domestic abuse victims than any other mental health condition. They noted conclusions from Forbes et al (2014) that health service staff fail to identify the symptoms of PTSD in the context of domestic violence; and also, the need for health services to put in place specific domestic abuse trauma interventions for victims (Duxbury, 2006).

Aitken and Munro (2018) extend the concept of PTSD, describing complex PTSD as an independent condition within the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems (ICD-11). This was also noted by Bates et al. (2021) on the basis that complex post- traumatic stress disorder (C-PTSD) is likely to include many of the adverse psychological impacts experienced by women who have experienced abuse (and should be recognised as a form of 'bodily injury' for the purposes of criminal liability).

Hedtke et al. (2008) studied a sample of 4,008 women over a two-year period and found that a) women with histories of sexual assault were three times more likely to have PTSD and twice as likely to have depression than those without; and b) that victims who had been subjected to multiple and/or repeated abuses were most likely to experience PTSD, depression; and also, substance use problems. The severity of these co-morbidities increased incrementally with the increase in concurrent abuses and/or repetition of abuses over time. Furthermore, Hedtke et al concluded that the strongest and most consistent risk factors for PTSD and depression was experiencing both physical and sexual assault in multiple forms of violence.

Feeling states

Aitken and Munro (2018) reported that 96% of the victims in their research who reported suicidal thoughts or acts, said they felt despairing or hopeless. Zeppegno et al. (2021) found that feeling burdensome is also significantly correlated with suicidality, including in patients with disordered eating, especially those with anorexia (in relation to which symptoms might represent anger and hatred towards the self). In support of the latter perspective, Yen and Siegler (2003) and Chang et al. (2014) found that forgiveness of self/ alleviating feelings of self-blame and promoting the motivation to change reduced or eliminated the positive link between domestic abuse and suicidality.

Øverup et al., (2017) investigated the relationship between burdensomeness, which can be interpreted as having a negative relationship with self) and attachment anxiety (i.e., disruption in their relationships with others). They reported that there is a link between individuals having less self-compassion, feeling less belonging, and experiencing a higher level of burdensomeness. Importantly, Øverup et al. found that these factors were associated with increased depressive symptoms. This replicates predictions from Attachment Theory (Bowlby, 1973). Joiner (2007) identified the same two 'feeling states' (thwarted belongingness and perceived burdensomeness) as key predictors of suicidal behaviour, together with two other elements: a desire for suicide (not wanting to be in the world), and capacity (the means) for suicide. This was supported by Van Heeringen (2018).

Van Heeringen (2018), Van Orden et al. (2010) and Hagan et al. (2016) agreed that thwarted belongingness (which they described as 'feeling alone') and feeling of like a burden were contributors to suicide. The latter two research teams added a sense of hopelessness (being helpless/powerless and with no prospect of this changing in the future). Extending the idea of belongingness, Fedina et al (2021) looked at gentrification and found lower levels of neighbourhood cohesion were associated with higher levels of domestic abuse. Furthermore, neighbourhood disconnectedness worsened psychological distress symptoms and suicide risk most strongly among individuals exposed to domestic abuse.

Meadows et al. (2005) found that in their small sample of low income, African American domestic abuse victims (women), those who strongly espoused hope, spiritual well-being, self-efficacy, coping, social support from family members, social support from friends and effectiveness of obtaining resources were least likely to be suicidal. However, in line with the findings from the other studies, only hope and support from family differentiated those who made serious/multiple suicide attempts from those who did not.

Klonsky & May (2015), theorise that the combination of feeling pain and hopelessness is what develops experiencing suicidal ideation. Though they acknowledge that feelings of belongingness and burdensomeness contribute to suicidal ideation, they suggest that these feelings are not always present in experiences of suicidal ideation, but connectedness is an important protective factor in those at risk of death by suicide. They also theorise that the trajectory from ideation to an attempt of suicide is influenced by the combination of personal traits, learned experiences, and practical means, which can create the capacity to overcome the pain and fear involved in attempting to take one's life.

Findings: Coping strategies

Substance use

In a Canadian study, Espinet et al. (2019) found that the lifetime suicide risk for individuals with substance use disorder was 5 – 10 times higher than the 3 – 5% risk in the general population; for individuals with alcohol abuse problems, it was 10 times higher; for those using opiates it was 14 times higher and for those with mixed-drug use it was 17 times higher. In addition, Espinet et al. reported that these individuals made multiple suicide attempts. Bolton et al. (2006) focused on domestic abuse victims and similarly concluded that self-medication through drug and alcohol use increases the risk of suicidality. Aitken and Munro (2018) found problematic alcohol and drug use were significantly associated with suicidality.

Ragin et al. (2002) interviewed 122 mostly African American and Latina women, and found that the 45 who attempted suicide, were more likely to report substance abuse among both first-degree (specifically fathers) and second-degree relatives, than were women without such suicide attempt histories. They were also more likely to report witnessing the physical abuse of their mothers (see subsection 5.2 for information about the impact of childhood trauma, (including witnessing domestic abuse, on lifetime suicidality).

Self harm

Self-harm is a key risk factor for suicide (Hawton et al., 2014; Whitlock et al., 2015; Chan et al., 2016). In a relatively large, ten-year study in England, Hawton et al. (2015) found the risk of suicide in the first year following self-harm to be 49 times greater than the general population risk of suicide in England and Wales. While the absolute risk of suicide was greater in males, the risk relative to that in the general population was higher in females. Whitlock et al. (2015) note that self-harm and suicidality have common risk factors, such as, experience of trauma, abuse, or chronic stress, few effective mechanisms for dealing with emotional stress, poor relationships or isolation, depression or anxiety and feelings of worthlessness.

Findings: Frequency and severity of abuse***Duration of abuse and multiple abusers/abuses***

Aitken and Munro (2018) found a link between the duration of domestic abuse and suicidality. This relationship appeared to be strongest for physical or financial abuse. In their research sample, the mean duration of physical abuse for those in the suicidal group was just over four years compared with just under three years for those in the non-suicidal group. In addition, victims who had been abused by more than one person were more likely than those who had been abused by a single perpetrator to express suicidality (approximately 16% of victims in the suicidal group had been abused by more than one person compared with 8% of the non-suicidal group).

Reporting on the WHO's data on the health effects of domestic abuse, Potter et al. (2021) noted that all forms of domestic abuse were associated with poorer health outcomes, however, two categories of combined abuse were the most damaging. The most common category was any abuse combined with sexual assault, which was associated with the poorest health, including memory loss, suicidal ideation and attempted suicide (see subsection 5.2 for an exploration of the traumatic impact of rape). This was similar to the finding by Hedtke et al. (2008) that physical and sexual assault together were the strongest risk factors for PTSD and depression. Potter et al. reported that the second most common category, with the next poorest outcomes (again including memory loss, suicidal ideation and attempted suicide) was the combination of physical and emotional and psychological abuse. See subsection 5.1 for an exploration of the dismantling of identity.

Being subjected to life-threatening abuse

Sato-DiLorenzo and Sharps (2007) found that women who experience life-threatening domestic abuse assaults are significantly more likely to attempt suicide than victims of less dangerous behaviour to attempt suicide during their lifetime. Their finding was that domestic abuse victims who fear for their lives may attempt suicide in an attempt to reclaim control over an unpredictable and uncontrollable situation. Hedtke et al. (2008) concluded that there is a link between the seriousness of the threat to life and the degree of mental ill health experienced by a victim – in the form of PTSD, anxiety and depression. This impact from severe (and chronic domestic violence), are in turn risk factors for suicidal ideation (Johnson et al, 2008).

Aitken and Munro (2018) found that the strongest correlations with suicidality were for physical abuse, being strangled, kicked, or suffocated – together with any report of sexual abuse. Also, for psychological abuse, isolation from family and friends and experiencing threats of harm with a weapon, threats to kill a family member; and any report of financial abuse. In terms of mental health/psychological symptoms, problematic alcohol and drug use were significant. Isolation was also associated with suicidality.

Kuehn et al. (2020) highlight the finding from a significant number of studies that one of the most robust predictors of future suicide is a previous suicide attempt, regardless of the cause. They add that some research has identified the average time period between a non-fatal suicide attempt and death by suicide is one year. Kuehn et al. concluded that thoughts of suicide and suicide attempts should never be dismissed as 'merely a cry for help', because doing so risks ignoring those whose psychological pain had reached the point that they are likely to take their own lives in the future (Kuehn et al., 2020).

Limitations

All research has limitations and this is especially true of the available research on domestic abuse due largely to under and inconsistent reporting. Rowlands et al. (2020) highlighted this in their study of reporting of lifetime domestic abuse among 7,917 young women. The participants completed three surveys: at the first survey, 32% reported experiencing domestic abuse with a current or recent partner, of these one third did not report domestic abuse 12 months later. Additionally, Rowlands et al. (2020) found that the women who inconsistently reported a history of domestic abuse were also less likely to report suicidal ideation, self-harm, illicit drug use, and smoking at the 12-month follow-up. For the same reason, there is also a difficulty in obtaining sufficiently nuanced information, in our case, to understand the specific relationship between domestic abuse and suicide.

Findings from research into suicidality linked to domestic abuse, highlights variation between countries and between different racial groups, minority status and cultural beliefs on suicidality and suicide, in different countries (World Health Organisation, 2021). To limit such variation, this review focused on research undertaken in the UK or in Western societies with profiles broadly similar to the UK e.g., USA (with findings from a few other country studies where none was identified for the UK/similar societies).

A final crucial limitation was that within the time and resource constraints of this rapid evidence review, it was not possible to go beyond broad studies of 'domestic abuse' and 'suicide' and explore the discrete areas of research into the impacts of the different forms of abuse to understand their importance in the aetiology of victim suicide. Focusing on these areas in future research could bring to light the nuances which we anticipate could significantly progress understanding of the links between domestic abuse and victim suicide. The findings from the fieldwork in this project support this view.

Summary

From this rapid review of the literature on potential links between domestic abuse and suicide, it appears possible to draw the following summary conclusion:

Studies into non-fatal strangulation have identified the life-threatening experience as a strong contributor to victim suicidality (Aitken & Munro). It may be that as an effective facilitator of coercion and control, non-fatal strangulation may influence the fact that coercion and control was found by Bates et al (2021) to be three times more likely to have been experienced by victims in domestic abuse suicides than in domestic abuse homicides. Financial abuse forms part of coercion and control, Aitken and Munro found it to have been experienced by a third of victims and to have contributed to their suicidality. Coercion and control involves emotional and psychological manipulation and abuse, and is experienced by between 88-91% of victims (SafeLives, 2019; Aitken & Munro). An abuse which appears to be highly correlated with victim suicide is sexual assault/rape (Coke et al., 2002; Cavanaugh, 2011).

In terms of emotional and psychological impact, depression is linked to severity of the abuse (Sato- DiLorenzo & Sharps, 2007) and suicide (Devries, 2013). Chandan et al., (2019) found that domestic abuse victims were three times more likely to have depression than non-abused women. Hedtke et al. found a correlation between PTSD and depression and repetition of abuse, multiple concurrent forms of abuse, and inclusion in the multiple abuses of physical and sexual abuse/rape.

The most likely feeling states to predict suicide have been identified as despair and hopelessness; although this often includes panic, terror and/or past traumas (e.g., in childhood) (Pilowsky et al., 2006; Aitken & Munro, 2018). Hopelessness has been strongly linked to a lack of 'belongingness' (i.e., disrupted relationships/isolation) (Lineham & Nielsen, 1981). These conclusions fit relatively well with Klonsky and May's (2015) framework of four key contributors to suicidality: physical and emotional/psychological pain, hopelessness (including powerlessness/helplessness), lack of connectedness (disrupted relationships and isolation), and suicide capability (the means to take one's own life). Added to this has been 'burdensomeness' (Zeppegno, 2021), which is associated with self-hatred (Van Ziegler, 2003; Chang et al., 2014). There is a link between individuals having less self-compassion, feeling less belongingness, and experiencing a higher level of burdensomeness; and these factors were associated with increased depressive symptoms (Øverup et al., 2017). This replicates predictions from Attachment Theory (Bowlby, 1973) and prompts consideration of the importance of relationships in the maintenance of individual's health and wellbeing, particularly in terms of self-identity.

In relation to coping strategies, substance use appears to be significantly associated with suicidality (Espinet et al., 2019; Aitken & Munro, 2018). Self-harm is also a predictor of suicide (Hawton et al., 2015; Whitlock et al., 2015; Chan et al., 2016) and shares common risk factors with suicidality.

The findings from this Rapid Evidence Review inform both the fieldwork and quantitative analysis presented in this report. The types of abuse and emotional states identified in the literature as being linked to suicide provide a foundation for discussions with previous victims of domestic abuse, guiding the exploration of these factors through lived experience. The quantitative evaluation expands on the current understanding of the prevalence, complexity, and temporal dynamics of suicide following domestic abuse—an aspect that is rarely explored in existing literature.

Fieldwork

The focus of the fieldwork included whether domestic abuse increases the risk of victims dying by suicide; whether victims with particular demographics are more likely to attempt suicide, whether certain forms of domestic abuse are more likely to result in the victim dying by suicide and whether forced marriage/honour-based violence increases domestic abuse-related suicide.

Conceptual framework

We commenced the fieldwork by developing a conceptual framework for exploring and illustrating the relationships between factors that could constitute or contribute to, a link between a victim experiencing domestic abuse and the victim attempting suicide.

Conceptual frameworks are a form of theory of change in so far as they articulate assumptions about causal relationships between initial contributing factors or inputs, the interim impacts or outputs, and final outcomes. These assumptions can then be tested in the research.

Initial inputs: the initiating inputs were taken to be the abusive behaviors of the perpetrators. The impact of these may be exacerbated by gender norms such as, a patriarchal culture (including forced marriage); the victim having a disability; the victim having caring responsibilities; and/or the victim having adverse childhood experiences. The abusive behaviors of the perpetrators which we used as a prompt for the participants were initially derived from the forms of abuse identified in Bates et al. (2021). Additional forms of abuse emerged from the victims' narratives, and these were included. The abuses included forms of: physical abuse, emotional abuse, coercion and control, sexual assault, and stalking/surveillance.

Interim impacts: the interim impacts or outputs were identified as the victims' emotional and psychological impacts from the abuse – which were assumed to be negative. A further assumption was that the negativity could be mitigated if victims were able to support themselves with effective coping strategies.

The emotional and psychological impacts which we used as a prompt for the participants were adapted from Lester (2021). We also included contributors to suicidal ideation and potentially death by suicide, identified in other research (Neimeyer, 1984; Shneidman, 1996, Corriera et al., 2014). Our list of impacts were: hopelessness, fear, unbearableness, cognitive constriction, helplessness, entrapment, burdensomeness, emotional dysregulation, low self-esteem, shame, and imposter syndrome/perfectionism.

For this research we chose situational coping and listed coping strategies likely to be specific to domestic abuse. Our rationale was that focusing on what the victims did, rather than aspects of who they are, may have more potential for the development of tools to assess risk. Accordingly, the coping mechanisms which we used as a prompt for the participants were: avoidance, religion, confiding in someone, finding practical help, self-distraction, denial, venting negative emotion, substance use, withdrawal, self-blame, and self-harm. It should be noted that these coping mechanisms are not solutions and can therefore only ever be helpful/positive in the short-term. Some of the maladaptive ways are potentially seriously dangerous depending on the intensity of their use.

Final outcomes: the interim impacts were assumed to influence the final outcomes. As noted above, the final outcomes were anticipated to be one of the following: a victim having experienced no suicidal ideation; the victim having experienced suicidal ideation but not having attempted suicide; or the victim having attempted suicide. An additional assumption was made that depending on the degree to which the interim impacts were or could be mitigated, a final outcome may be expected to be influenced by/include, an increased likelihood of successful separation.

This conceptual framework was used to develop the fieldwork interview questions. An exception to this is the fact that adverse childhood experiences were not identified as potentially impactful in the original conceptual framework and in consequence did not generate questions in the semi-structured interview guide.

Methodology

A qualitative approach was adopted gathering insights directly from previous victims into their experience of domestic abuse. We hoped to find patterns within the previous victims' narratives which might suggest links between forms of abuse, the impact of abuse on victims and thoughts of suicide or suicide attempts. Accordingly, we asked about the impact the domestic abuse had on the previous victims, what coping strategies they were able to deploy, whether and who they received help from, and then whether they had suicidal thoughts or had attempted suicide. Clearly, gathering data via interviews meant that cases of those who had died by suicide were outside the scope of this research.

Our approach in the interviews was unusually unstructured for two reasons. The first reason was that we were keen to avoid missing potentially valuable information exchanges by putting limits to the discussion. We approached the previous victims with the perspective that they are true experts by experience. The second reason was that we were conscious of the extremely sensitive nature of the subject matter and were aware that for some of the previous victims the time period between leaving the abusive relationship and talking to us was only a few months. Accordingly, we were careful to allow participants to choose when and how to offer personal information and to avoid controlling the interview.

Participants

Recruitment: The principal fieldwork data were collected from 34 previous victims of domestic abuse and the secondary fieldwork data were collected from two families who had lost a family member to suicide where that family member had experienced domestic abuse. All participation was voluntary. The participants had received information about the research and an invitation to participate via the domestic abuse organisation which was supporting them in the Birmingham area.

Ethnicity: In addition to engaging previous victims from the range of ethnic and cultural backgrounds who were likely to access generic domestic abuse support services, we were particularly keen to talk to previous victims from South Asian communities. This was because we wanted to understand the extent to which so called honour-based violence and abuse might influence a victim to think about suicide. Domestic abuse victims' ethnic and cultural background can be important because the cultural meaning and degree to which suicidal behaviour may be acceptable differs between communities, and suicidality can be highly stigmatized (Bertolote et al., 2005; Alem et al., 2007a; Devries, 2011). The voluntary nature of the participation meant that scope for purposive sampling was limited but we were able to address this by approaching domestic abuse organisations specialising in support for South Asian domestic abuse victims. See Figure 1 for information participant ethnicity and Figure 2 for information regarding type of abuse experienced.

Figure 1: Participant's self-reported ethnicity:

Figure 2: Forms of abuse experienced by participants.

44% of participants experienced honour-based violence and abuse and 56% experienced domestic abuse.

Disability: One participant described having disabilities or learning difficulties when they met the abuser. She has been diagnosed with bipolar disorder and Emotionally Unstable Personality Disorder (EUPD).

Sexual Orientation: All the participants described themselves as heterosexual.

Gender: All participants were female. The participants are referred to as 'she/her' in the rest of this report.

Relationship status: Two participants were in a relationship with the abuser, but not married, all others were married.

Age: The ages of participants ranged between 23 and 54 years, with an average of 37.

Bereaved families: The bereaved family members were recruited in the same way as the previous victims of domestic abuse. One family had lost a female family member and the other a male.

Data Collection and Analysis

Interviews were conducted by telephone to preserve previous victim anonymity and recorded with handwritten notes to provide a measure of participant anonymity and confidence. The data were manually coded using categories which closely reflected the prompts for the initial inputs, interim impacts and final outcomes listed in the conceptual framework. Additional themes were identified as they emerged from the previous victims' narratives. Notwithstanding the small sample size in the fieldwork for this research, we quantified the previous victims' responses and present the data in this report together with percentages. Subject to the reminder of the small sample size, the percentages facilitate comparison between the different sub- groups of respondents: previous victims without suicidal ideation or attempts, previous victims with suicidal ideation but no attempts and previous victims who attempted suicide.

The analytical approach combined a phenomenological focus on the individual cases to understand the underlying structure or essence of the previous victim's experience and constant comparative analysis, finding patterns and commonalities within their experience. To promote interpretive accuracy when lifting data from the interview responses, a holistic case study was constructed for each previous victim. This process preserves a sense of the previous victim as a whole person in a social context and mitigates possible fragmentation of meaning when analysing deconstructed responses under the coding categories.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for this research was provided by the University of Birmingham STEM ethics committee. The participating previous victims and families were approached via the organisations supporting them; they had access to information about the research and the semi-structured interview questions. Prior to acceptance into the study the participants were risk assessed to be sure that they were in a position to benefit from, rather than being harmed through participation in the research. The participants were supported by their support workers immediately pre- and post- interview, as well as receiving a follow-up call the next day. It was extremely important to the research team that the previous victims would experience their participation as beneficial to themselves. Feedback from the previous victims was that they felt 'happy and strong' after sharing their story; that they felt that 'someone was finally listening to them'; that they were 'so grateful' to be part of the research; that they felt 'some closure' after the interview and that they were 'excited to have been involved' with the research and felt 'lighter' after the interview.

Findings: Previous Victims

The fieldwork findings are presented using the conceptual framework. The tables in this section provide the data for all the previous victims and in the three categories shown below:

Participants who did not have suicidal thoughts or a non-fatal suicide attempt.

Participants who thought about suicide but did not attempt it.

Participants who thought about and attempted suicide.

Importantly for the generalisability of our findings, we note that the experiences described by the survivors are typical rather than unusual for survivors of domestic abuse.

Findings: The abuse

The initial inputs comprise the abuses experienced by participants; sourced from the those identified in Bates et al. (2021). The prevalence of these, and the most common forms of abuse which emerged from the previous victims' narratives, are set out in this section in Tables 1 to 5 together (the abuses emerging from the survivors' narratives are italicised in the tables).

Physical abuse experienced by participants:

Participants were asked what forms of physical abuse they had experienced. Analysis of their responses is set out in Tables 1a to 1g. The difference between the survivors who did not experience suicidal thoughts or attempt suicide and those who attempted suicide appears to have been influenced by the perpetrator attempting to kill them (other than through non-fatal strangulation and use of a weapon). The proportion of these survivors who attempted suicide was 82% compared to 50% of survivors without suicidal ideation/attempt (a 32-percentage point difference).

Table 1a: Physical violence experienced by survivors

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
32	94%	4	100%	18	95%	10	91%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"The abuse got worse till he was hitting, kicking and beating me. It got even worse when I had my daughter. I remember him beating me up in the car for about 40 minutes. I was completely bruised up. He would say: 'I'm going to kill you.' when he was hitting me."

"He pinned my head down and strangled me from behind. Another time he used his fist to try to bash my head in. I thought he was going to kill me."

"He hit me full in the face with a head butt. He pushed me down the stairs, he smashed up the sides of my face, he hit me with coat hangers and he threw bottles at me."

"The physical violence was very, very bad. He spilt my head open and I would see the blood spattering. Now I live with scars on my forehead and face from the different times he smashed my face and head up."

Table 1b: Non-fatal strangulation experienced by participants:

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
17	50%	3	75%	6	32%	5	45%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"Strangulation, he applied the same pressure each time and just extended the length of time he held on. If it was a small annoyance, he would do it for a couple of seconds. But there were times when I would be thinking 'he's not going to let go'. He may kill me intentionally, but he may also just get it wrong and kill me."

"He took drugs. That is against my religion. The first time I asked him to stop, he strangled me. After that he hit me and strangled me all the time."

"He strangled me often and punched me in the head because the bruises don't show through your hair. The strangling doesn't show and neither did the rapes. But he did also break my fingers and toes."

"He strangled me all the time so I always had bruises round my neck. I used to wear polo necks and scarves all the time. I had to use a really expensive foundation (£40) to cover it."

Table 1c: Attempts to kill (other than non-fatal strangulation and use of a weapon) experienced by participants:

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
22	65%	2	50%	11	58%	9	82%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"He tried to kill me in different ways, he forced pills down my throat, he strangled/ hung me, and he tried to drown me in the bath."

"He would punch and kick me. He stood on me and cracked my head."

"He beat me, punching and kicking and he also choked me (non-fatal strangulation). He threw cups at me and smashed plates over my head. One day he tried to suffocate me with a pillow."

Table 1d: Abuse with a weapon experienced by participants:

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
16	47%	3	75%	6	32%	4	36%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"He got sexual gratification from transsexuals, so he planned to give me testosterone therapy injections to change me into a male."

"He stabbed me six times with a bread knife."

"He threw furniture at me e.g., a wooden stool, a solid wooden box, bottles, glasses of wine. Sometimes he did this during the night while I was asleep."

"My life was constantly in danger. Beatings. Being forcibly held down. Threatened with an axe which he kept by the bed. He made very violent threats to my life. He held me against the doorframe naked. He tried to drown me in the shower."

Table 1e: Threat to maim, rape or kill experienced by participants:

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
19	56%	2	50%	10	53%	7	64%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"He would get the iron out and put it on to warm up. He would hold it to my face. I would do whatever he wanted before he actually burned me..."

"He said 'I will get someone to do an acid attack on you. No-one, not even your friends will want to look at you, let alone go out with you'. He knew how much fear that would create for me. For years I have been trying to avoid people in public for fear of the attack. I did not tell the boys and I think they have found some of my behaviour strange."

"I didn't leave because he used to say: 'If you leave me, I will burn the house down and kill the children.' Then when I decided to leave anyway, there was no Refuge that would take my 14 year old son and I couldn't leave him."

Table 1f: Domestic servitude/unrealistic expectations experienced by participants:

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
11	32%	2	50%	6	32%	4	36%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"I had a really difficult pregnancy due to stress and exhaustion, which led to high blood pressure and pre-eclampsia. That was because of the criticism and because I was still doing everything in the house. When I was 24 weeks pregnant, he attacked me and I fell. He dragged me across the room by my hair. My daughters were crying."

"I was doing the cooking and cleaning, looking after all his needs and the baby's, and doing my university work. He was home every weekend so I asked him to help look after the baby. He said: 'you are my slave, I own you' and he beat me."

"With all the rapes he got me pregnant four times in six years. It was very hard on my body. He didn't want to know about raising the children and he made me do all the housework. He would say, 'all you're good for is cooking and cleaning.' Breastfeeding was impossible because of the stress."

Table 1g: Abuse by several perpetrators (e.g., family members) experienced by participants:

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
15	44%	1	25%	10	53%	4	36%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

“If I confronted him about anything, like when I caught him with his girlfriend, he would strangle me. His mother always supported him.”

“He raped me. Every time I resisted, he called his father saying how useless and worthless I was and getting advice about how to control me. I was hurting all the time. I stayed away from everyone because of the shame and humiliation.”

“As soon as I became pregnant, I lost all privacy from his mother in particular. Mother and son ‘ganged up’ on me. She came to all my maternity appoints and texted professionals beforehand to get time with them without me in the room. After I had the baby, they told the midwife that I was a bad mother and they needed to be there to supervise.”

“In this marriage we lived with his parents and his brother. They all treated me as if I was nobody. The father and brother hit me but my mother-in-law was the main abuser. When the police came to stop him beating me the night I left, his extended family all came to the house to stop the police protecting me. The police had to call for backup to disperse the crowd.”

“He and his brother kidnapped me and kept me in a locked in a room and raped me. He was very abusive. His mother was also very abusive.”

Emotional abuse experienced by participants:

Participants were asked what forms of emotional abuse they had experienced. Analysis of their responses is set out in Tables 2a to 2e. The difference between the victims who did not experience suicidal thoughts or attempt suicide and those who attempted suicide appears to have been influenced by:

The perpetrator telling everyone in the victim’s social network and the services, that the victim ‘was crazy’. The proportion of these victims who attempted suicide was 82% compared to 50% of victims without suicidal ideation/attempt (a 32-percentage point difference).

The perpetrator manipulating the victim’s children and/or using the children to manipulate the victim. The proportion of these victims who attempted suicide was 82% compared to 57% of victims without suicidal ideation/attempt (a 32-percentage point difference).

The perpetrator abusing the children. The proportion of these victims who attempted suicide was 82% compared to 50% of victims without suicidal ideation/attempt (a 32-percentage point difference).

Table 2a: Humiliation and criticism

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
34	100%	4	100%	19	100%	11	100%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"I would be in public with him, and he would start shaking and stomping his foot. I would be so scared I would wet myself. People would be staring. Then he would say: 'Look what you've done. You're disgusting, look at you, you're a fucking mess!' and everyone would stand there looking at me...humiliated."

"He 'put me down' alone and in front of others all the time. It was humiliation. He criticised my makeup, my looks; calling me names like 'slut' and 'whore'. It was embarrassment all the time. I felt 'less than' everyone else I knew."

"He would tell other people that I was a sex maniac. He would give false descriptions of me sexually and my 'performance' in bed to everyone we knew."

"He criticised me for 'never cooking proper food for the children'. I was careful how I fed the children because my mother traumatised me by forcing food into me. When he was left alone with the boys he forced them to eat. When he could, the older one ate the younger one's food, to help him cope."

"Nothing about me was good enough. So, I spent all my money on skin treatments and cosmetic surgery. He humiliated me in front of everyone about my face and body."

"The criticism was relentless. I could not take the mind games anymore. When I said I needed a break, he and his family said: 'You're the one who needs their mind seen to'. I became seriously suicidal."

Table 2b: Mind games and the perpetrator telling everyone the victim 'was crazy'

Participants experience	All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
	Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
<i>Mind games (gaslighting)</i>	33	97%	4	100%	19	100%	10	91%
<i>Abuser told everyone the victim 'was crazy'</i>	24	71%	2	50%	15	75%	9	82%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"He re-wrote history, recalling our conversations and convincing me that my memory of what was said was wrong."

"The physical abuse is bad, but the mental abuse is far worse. He started moving things around the house and when I said something about it he would say I was imagining it, I was crazy, nothing had moved. I didn't realise it was abuse, I didn't even realise it was happening to me."

"The mind games included moving things in the house and when I noticed something had been moved, he would say it hadn't moved, that I was imagining things. Also, lying, so that I never knew what was true and what wasn't – about him (e.g., his history), what he had done or was going to do, who he had seen, what he thought or said about anything. When he is the only person, you see and talk to, you end up not knowing what to believe, what the truth is."

"He manipulated me, confusing me. He lied all the time; and he was always telling me what I saw wasn't real e.g., if I caught him doing drugs, he would say it was just 'in my head' and tell everyone that I was making up stories that weren't true. I started screen-shotting messages to try to remember what was true and what was lies."

"If we were around other people, he would whisper things like 'you slag' under his breath so only I could hear him. I would get angry, and he would say 'See I told you she was crazy'."

"My parents and all the family believed him when he told them I was crazy. He told them that he was always having to advise me how to behave."

Table 2c: Threats to abuse family members/pets

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
15	44%	1	25%	8	42%	6	55%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"If I resisted in any way he would say 'your child will suffer'. He kept threatening death on my child (our child) and my parents, as well as me. He also threatened curses through witchcraft."

"I stayed because he threatened to get social services to take my children taken away from me by telling them about my mental health problems. I left when he got worse and started threatening to kill my daughter."

"He made threats to kill my brothers and parents to stop me doing or saying things; and he would say: 'If you ever leave or I see you with another man, I'll kill you'."

Table 2d: Threats relating to honour-based violence

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
6	18%	1	25%	3	16%	2	18%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"My family and community said that a successful woman is a married woman (we are raised to know that you must not get divorced). So, I thought: "This is marriage, and the abuse is going to go on forever". There was no way out, I couldn't go back the only escape was ending my life."

"However, he treated me, I had to take it for the sake of family honour. He would say: 'don't speak in front of me, you're already divorced and you don't want to break down this marriage.'

Table 2e: Manipulation of/via children and abuse of the children

Participants experience	All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
	Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
Manipulation of/via children	24	71%	1	25%	14	74%	9	82%
Abuse of the children	25	81%	2	50%	14	74%	9	82%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"Then he gave my nine-year-old son a phone and told him to record me in my mum's house. I didn't know. My son took the film to his father. When my husband used the film to attack me, my son was confused and upset. He wanted to please his dad, but he didn't want to be the cause of his father attacking me."

"My daughter told the school: 'I hate my life because of my stepdad; he slapped my bottom; I'm scared of him etc and each time the school called him, and he allayed their fears. She was presenting textbook child sexual abuse symptoms and disclosures and he just persuaded them it was me, because I 'had mental health problems'."

"He would hold me down and go to strangle me and he would say: 'See the children are watching!'. "He raped me a lot and filmed it and sent it to the children."

"He raped me all the time – sometimes 4/5 times a night., he would pour vodka down my throat and then rape me. He invited my child into our bed and then started to sexually assault me in front of the child."

In most cases the victims did not tell services about the perpetrator's abuse of the children. The reasons for this include that the victims feared that they would be accused of not protecting the children or of neglecting them, with a potential consequence of the children being removed by social services. A victim who was in contact with services during the relationship said: "I could not be honest with them because I was too scared that they would take the children." This fear was fuelled by the perpetrators as a means of coercion and in order to avoid the household being scrutinised by children's social care. The perpetrator also benefits in the longer term because the police then do not have a record of abuse directed by him at the children if/when he seeks post separation contact and/or custody in the Family Courts.

Table 2f: Exhaustion including through disrupted sleep

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
25	74%	3	75%	16	84%	6	55%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"I was very, very tired from cooking, cleaning, begging for money for the children, worrying about debts; and always, the abuse. It was constant pressure. I had no time to play with my children or read to them or talk with them. He isolated me from them."

"He raped me. It was relentless – I was so tired, I couldn't sleep knowing that he was going to do it to me."; and "He would also rape me when I was sleeping. I couldn't sleep. I was exhausted."; and "He raped me when I was asleep; so, I was too scared to go to sleep. I became completely exhausted – and it didn't stop because you fall asleep when you are so tired."

"He used sleep deprivation to wear me down. I was working long hours as a full-time academic, I was also doing all the household chores. He would wake me – the good dad who had heard his son – and tell me I was a bad mum for not responding to my child when he needed me in the night. My mum stayed over several times and noticed that he was waking the child and then coming in to wake me..."

Coercion and control experienced by participants:

Participants were asked what forms of coercion and control they had experienced. Analysis of their responses is set out in Tables 3a to 3f. The difference between the victims who did not experience suicidal thoughts or attempt suicide and those who attempted suicide appears to have been influenced by the perpetrator subjecting the victim to reproductive coercion and abuse. The proportion of these victims who attempted suicide was 64% compared to 25% of victims without suicidal ideation/attempt (a 39-percentage point difference). However, the anomaly here is the victims who experienced suicidal ideation but who did not attempt suicide despite experiencing reproductive coercion and control. The proportion of these victims was 84% compared to the 25% of victims without suicidal ideation/attempt (a 59-percentage point difference).

Table 3a: Isolation from friends and family

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
34	100%	4	100%	19	100%	11	100%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"It was the control, with everything going through his mother. They bought all my clothes, she dressed me, they went through all my laundry and threw away things they didn't like. She chaperoned me if we went out. I wasn't allowed any friends or to see my family."

"All my friends and family turned against me because he told them lies, like: 'she's jealous of you'. I stopped trusting them because I didn't know what he had told them and so I couldn't trust that they were on my side."

"He told everyone my children's school: 'You don't want to talk to her, she's got serious mental health problems'. The result was that none of the other mothers would talk to me, and they wouldn't let their children play with my children."

Table 3b: Financial control

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
34	100%	4	100%	19	100%	11	100%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"He used my cards, so the spending was all in my name. He left me with £20k of debt. I have that debt now – I have lost any chance of financial freedom."

"He was working but I had no money, I was too scared to ask him why he had sent all the money back to Sudan. I got food from my mother and sister and money from my brother. I had two children with 11 months between them."

"He took all my money. He called me a 'money dupe'". *

* (a term popularised by the online game: 'Roblox Lumber Tycoon 2', referring to people who are easily deceived into handing over money).

"He took all the money. He took the children's money – saying he was 'just borrowing it', but he never paid it back. He sold my car and kept the money. He transferred the house into his name (on the deeds) so that he owned it."

"I have Disability Living Allowance and a bank account. He took over all the money. I had to beg for money to feed the children."

Table 3c: Control of behaviour in the home

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
34	100%	4	100%	19	100%	11	100%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"I was locked in a room or in other rooms. I was not allowed a bed, had to sleep on the floor. He had a sexual fetish for very fat people, so he forced me to drink weight gain shakes. He wanted me to be very fat. I had no control over my own body."

"He controlled my behaviour in the house e.g. I could only shower/bath when he said I could. He controlled how much water in the bath and how long I could stay in for. Also, when and how long I could brush my teeth. I was not allowed to put Tampax in and had to ask to buy sanitary towels."

"He counted the used teabags to ensure that I only drank one cup of tea per day."

"Inside the house I had to ask to do anything. I wasn't allowed to disturb anything e.g., the toothpaste tube or wherever anything had been put down."

"It was little things – being forced to focus on the minutest detail of everything all the time – reprogrammes your brain. I started worrying and being anxious about every little thing. I was reduced to survival mode. I lost who I was."

Table 3d: Control of behaviour outside of the home

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
34	100%	4	100%	19	100%	11	100%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"Our lifestyle was soon a routine of abuse. Him hitting me and controlling my shopping and looking after the household, my clothes, what I ate, when I slept and when I got up, who I visited, where I went. He cut my contact with anyone I liked. I went straight from my parent's home to him. I had a strict upbringing; I didn't know any other ways of being."

"I went across the road to a party. He texted: 'come home. I'm going to kill you; you're going with other men and taking drugs.' From what he'd done to me before, I thought: 'I can't do this anymore.' I was terrified."

"Outside the house, he controlled who I saw. I wasn't allowed to talk to men or look at them, I had to look down all the time. I was only allowed to go out with him or with people he chose. He isolated me from my friends and my family."

"He allowed me no space at all e.g., he 'liked' the music I liked, and he joined the clubs I joined and came with me. He latched onto everything I was and did and sucked the energy out of it and me."

Table 3e: Forced marriage

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
4	12%	0	0%	1	5%	3	27%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"I told my parents I did not want to go through with the wedding. They dragged me into it – what I thought, what I wanted didn't matter."

"He was my family's choice. We didn't know each other at all. He never talked to me. He just swore at me and called me 'bad' names (in his language). I told my parents I can't live here with him. But they said I had to."

"As the wedding got closer, I started getting more and more anxious, scared and depressed. I realised I couldn't live with this guy. No-one would listen to me. I chose suicide with an overdose of paracetamol. When I didn't die, I just went through with it."

Table 3f: Reproductive coercion and abuse

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
24	71%	1	25%	16	84%	7	64%

"Close to term the family wanted the baby out of me. They started making me walk up and down the stairs and gave me 'Asian remedies' to drink to bring on birth. The pressure was unbearable, I had stress and heartburn."

"When I announced the second pregnancy, he said: 'I will kill this baby' and he beat me for two hours. Then he threw me down the stairs."

"The abuse started when I became pregnant. He said he didn't want a girl. He tried to force me to have an abortion. I said 'No', so, he beat me up."

"I am allergic to hormonal contraception, so I had the coil put in. He made me have it removed. But when I did get pregnant, he punched me in the stomach saying: 'I hope you miscarry'."

"He tried to make me have another baby by withholding my contraception and raping me, because he wanted a boy. So, I got myself sterilised. I got a really, really terrible beating for that."

Many of the victims talked about the attitude the perpetrators had towards women e.g. "He said all women must be controlled and that I would wish that I had behaved." and "Even now, after we have separated, he says he still 'owns' me."

Sexual assault experienced by participants:

Participants were asked whether they had experienced sexual assault and/or any online sexual abuse. Analysis of their responses is set out in Tables 4a and 4b. There was no significant difference between the groups of victims in relation to sexual assault because only one victim said that she was not raped by the perpetrator (in most cases this abuse was regular).

Participants did not disclose the rape to the police (or health services). It appears that the role of rape is similar to that of non-fatal strangulation in the sense that the impact on the victim is devastating, but there is no visible evidence of the abuse.

Table 4a: *Sexual assault/rape*

Participants experience	All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
	Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
<i>Physical (rape)</i>	33	97%	3	75%	19	100%	11	100%
<i>Online abuse</i>	2	6%	0	0%	1	5%	1	9%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

“When he started with the ‘angry voice’ and body movements and slamming doors. If someone scares you this much, you just want to disappear. My hands would go cold like they had been in a freezer and my spine would start to shiver. I know he was going to hold me down (strangle or rape). And afterwards he would laugh. He left no evidence [of the physical/sexual abuse] – it was like it was another thing that was in my head”.

“I would wake up in the morning tied to the bed. I couldn’t go to the loo. He would laugh at me. He was a ‘sexual controller’. It was sexual torture. He was very sexually violent. He would rape me. I would wake up in the night and he had a hand over my mouth and rape me. Then he would cuddle up and make me a cup of tea.”

“I was never allowed to say ‘no’ to sex – or even asked. It was like a ‘wank’. He would pull down my pyjama bottoms while I was asleep (2-3am in the night) and rape me; or grab my hair and push his penis down my throat. I would be vomiting and crying, and I would wet myself. He would be shouting ‘shut up, if you don’t do it, I’ll knock your teeth out. Afterwards I would run to the bathroom, to the toilet, he would follow me and force himself on me while I was on the toilet. It went on for years and years. In the end I learnt to be silent and motionless. Then he would call me a ‘cold bitch’.”

“All he did was rape me. When I was really ill he went further – anal sex. I was disgusted and the shame was unbearable.”

Table 4b: Online/videoed sexual assault/rape

Participants experience	All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
	Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
<i>Physical (rape)</i>	33	97%	3	75%	19	100%	11	100%
<i>Online abuse</i>	2	6%	0	0%	1	5%	1	9%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

“He humiliated me by filming himself raping me and then sharing the video with his friends and them all laughing at me.”

“He would drug me and then film intimate videos of me and send them to the children. Afterwards I would find his handprints on my thighs.”

Stalking/surveillance experienced by participants:

The victims were asked whether they had experienced stalking in person and/or ICT/online. Analysis of their responses is set out in Table 5. There was no significant difference between the groups of victims in relation to stalking because almost all of the victims described being stalked by the perpetrator in person and online.

Table 5: Stalking/surveillance

Participants experience	All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
	Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
Physical	31	91%	4	100%	17	89%	10	91%
Online	33	97%	4	100%	19	100%	10	91%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"He installed CCTV inside the house to monitor me."

"He stalked my son. He joined my son's online Pokemon Club and he also hacked into my son's school IT account and sent him messages."

"That started a two-year cycle of him stalking me and sucking me back in. I would close my Instagram account and open a new one but he always found me and was the first one trying to contact me."

"I found videos taken by him of me from 18 months before I met him, filmed from the house next door to mine. He bought the house next door and got a puppy. He used the puppy to ingratiate himself with my child and he hooked me in by inviting my child to help him walk the puppy. I wouldn't let my child go off with a 'strange' man, so I went along. He also befriended my brothers. That's how the relationship started."

Findings: Additional issues emerging from victims' narratives

Additional information emerged from the victims' narratives which appeared likely to have influenced the victims' thinking with respect to suicide. This was information about support the victim might have received from her parents and/or siblings and about her contact with the external world when she was experiencing domestic abuse. Also, information about her previous relationship experience.

Participants family relationships and relationship history:

This information emerged from the victim's narratives rather than being a response to a specific question. Analysis of their responses is set out in Tables 6a to 6e. The difference between the victims who did not experience suicidal thoughts or attempt suicide and those who attempted suicide appears to have been influenced by:

The participant's family pressuring her to stay with the perpetrator or to take him back when they knew about the abuse. The proportion of these victims who attempted suicide was 55% compared to 0% of the previous victims without suicidal ideation/attempt (a 55-percentage point difference).

The previous victim having had one or more previous relationships in which she had experienced domestic abuse. The proportion of these victims who attempted suicide was 36% compared to 0% of the victims without suicidal ideation/attempt (a 36-percentage point difference).

Four of the participants described discovering that they had been groomed into the relationship as a means for the perpetrator to acquire leave to remain in the UK. In all four cases the victim was pressured into pregnancy to create a 'right to family life' for the perpetrator.

Four of the participants described serious difficulties in getting professionals to believe them because the perpetrator held a position of trust e.g., a witness protection social worker supporting the victim who had left a previously abusive relationship; a GP lead for safeguarding, a youth worker in a Mosque, and a nurse/worker/teaching assistant.

Table 6a: Participant's family pressured her to stay/take him back

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
14	41%	0	0%	8	42%	6	55%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

After one of the incidents when he left me unconscious ... I told my mother but she wouldn't listen. Our mothers were badly treated, so abuse is regarded as 'normal'. Our mothers just say to us: 'He'll change'. But how? Abusers don't change! If you are lucky, they get tired when they get old."

"When I went crying to my family, they said it was my fault."

"He said: 'I will kill you if you leave'. I spoke to my mother. She said 'NEVER' leave him – you will be killed."

Table 6b: Participant had to cope with the perpetrator having other sexual relationships

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
14	41%	1	25%	9	45%	4	36%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"He would take me with him when he went to see friends and family, but he would be there with her and he was intimate with her in front of everyone and in front of me. He would also make me sit next to his cousin who wanted to do sexual things and accept it – I felt disgusted."

"He fell out with his girlfriend and she phoned me and told me everything about the relationship. It was so horrible I started throwing up."

"He raped me whenever he wanted to. Meanwhile he was having an affair."

Table 6c: Participant had a previous abusive relationship

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
8	24%	0	0%	4	21%	4	36%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"My previous partner would come home drunk and be very violent and abusive. He battered me, he strangled me, he bit my face; and he smashed the house up. He called me names. I used to hide in the bedroom with the door bolted."

"My first husband was convicted of ten counts of rape and beating – me; and the other abuses – emotional abuse and coercion/control."

"In my first relationship he was very physically abusive – beatings; stomping on my face. He pushed me to the ground and he raped me in front of our three year old daughter. When I heard from his friends that he was boasting he had 'fucked me', I knew I couldn't be more shamed and humiliated than I already was, so I went to the police, and he was convicted of rape."

Table 6d: Relationship was being used by the perpetrator to get leave to remain

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
4	12%	0	0%	4	21%	0	0%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"Our family only knew him for three months before the wedding. He was in England as a student. We did not know that he was here illegally. His plan was to come as a student, then marry to get a VISA to live in England. Everything he told me/us was lies."

“I thought he married me because he loved me; he told me he loved me. But it was all lies. It was all just to get permanent residency in the UK. His plan was to make himself look like a settled kind of guy, with a wife and kids here in the UK. It was my first relationship; but it turned out that he had left two little boys and a wife back in Pakistan.”

“While I was needed to sign his VISA application extensions, he ‘put up with me’, but as soon as he got the VISA everything changed. He started forcing big arguments on me, to get me to leave. I couldn’t leave because I had the children and wouldn’t be able to work, to support myself and them.”

“He had been really nice till I had the baby and he made sure it had his last name – then it became all about his VISA. He said he never loved me, he just wanted his papers.”

“Every time he bought the child something. He would want a photo of him and her. She would start crying and he would start cursing her. I realised that he was building up a record of a ‘happy family’ for his VISA application.”

Table 6e: *The perpetrator was a ‘trusted professional’*

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
4	12%	1	25%	0	0%	3	27%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

“He had a part-time job at the local youth centre teaching Islamic Studies. He used my religion against me; that’s what men do in Islam. Not allowing me to talk to any man in or outside of the family, even the GP and optician.”

“He was known to everyone as a kind community GP and he was the local safeguarding lead for the NHS. Shortly after we got together, he got me diagnosed as having bipolar disorder and classified as ‘vulnerable adult’ with mental health problems. After that I was not allowed to speak on my own behalf in medical appointments.”

“No-one listened to me. I called social services saying: ‘Help me’. But they would not believe me. They saw that he was a nursery nurse and later a teaching assistant and they regarded him as a trusted professional.”

“Telling someone was not possible, I was isolated from family and friends and all the professionals knew and liked him.”

Participants’ contact with the external world

This information emerged from the survivor’s narratives rather than being a response to a question. Analysis of their responses is set out in Tables 7a and 7b. The difference between the survivors who did not experience suicidal thoughts or attempt suicide and those who attempted suicide appears to have been influenced by the degree to which others who knew about the abuse acted to help the survivor. Three quarters of the group who attempted suicide told someone about the abuse compared to half of the survivors without suicidal ideation/attempt. Survivors described knowing that others had seen the signs of abuse (e.g., bruises on her face, neck and arms) and/or the survivor had disclosed the abuse, yet no-one acted on the information. This circumstance applied to 91% of survivors who attempted suicide compared to 50% of survivors who did not have suicidal thoughts or attempt suicide (a 41-percentage point difference).

Table 7a: The participant told someone about the abuse

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
19	56%	2	50%	10	50%	8	73%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"I talked to my mother and my sister about how he was controlling me. But my mother said that he I just being overprotective."

"These people are really good. They wear a mask in front of other people. He was always happy and bubbly and respectful to everyone. I told my brother what was going on and he said: 'No – he's such a nice, kind guy...' "

"At the support group I attended (for mothers whose children have a learning disability) the group leader saw the open wound on my arm and asked me what had happened. I told her the truth and she said: 'Shush, shush'. I was left thinking nobody cares – what's the point in going on."

Table 7b: There were signs for others OR the participant disclosed, but no-one acted on the information

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
20	59%	2	50%	9	45%	10	91%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"Physical abuse included regular non-fatal strangulation. People noticed the marks on my neck, but no-one took the trouble to ask about them. My work colleagues admitted afterwards that they had noticed but they were 'minding their own business'."

"He beat me up in front of friends and family for dinner. He was shouting abuse at me, hitting and kicking me, I was bleeding. Later his nephew went out and bought me a McDonalds because I didn't get any food."

"When he beat me, and I had black eyes and bruises. But I had to take the children to school. So, he told everyone there that I injured myself as part of my mental health problems. No-one asked me what happened."

Findings: The emotional and psychological impact

Feelings experienced by participants

The interim impacts were identified as the participants' feelings as a result of the abuse (the previous victims' descriptions of the emotional and psychological impact – as this requires conscious awareness, it may not have captured the full actual impact. The participants were asked what feelings they had experienced during the relationship as a result of the abuse. Analysis of their responses is set out in Tables 8a to 8g.

There was no significant difference between the groups of participants in relation to their feelings as a result of the abuse they experienced. However, the feelings not experienced by the three participants who did not have suicidal thoughts or attempt suicide, were burdensomeness, shame or that their life was unbearable. It might have been useful to ask participants about grief as research indicates that it has a powerful impact on individuals¹⁷ (Mughal et al., 2020) and a number of victims talked about how much they had lost.

Some of the women had lost their children:

"Two years ago, when we had the first lockdown, my daughter was with him and he refused to give her back. So, I've lost my daughter. None of the abuse was documented so my description of what happened is meaningless. To negotiate contact I would have to go to contact mediation, but I can't. I'm just struggling to cope. I feel like I can't breathe most of the time."

Other participants described losses such as:

"I had ten miscarriages from the abuse. He killed my babies – I didn't grieve. Now I am still crying." and "It came on top – realising: 'Oh my God, 15 years of my life. What has happened to me? I was really, really sobbing.'"

Table 8a: Feeling scared; including anxiety and panic attacks

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
34	100%	4	100%	19	100%	11	100%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"The fear was massive. It was what he would do in the relationship and what he would do if I tried to get rid of him. Those 'acid attack' threats were always there; they have never left me."

"He came up and gripped my neck from behind to strangle me. That was the first time – I had a panic attack. The panic attacks became constant. I became very anxious and depressed and stressed. Soon I started losing my hair in clumps."

"The feeling of real fear, terror, will live with me for the rest of my life."

"I was so shocked that someone would do the sexual abuse [rape] he did to me. I was really scared. I became so submissive, it was abject, crawling humiliation. He's still in my head all the time."

Table 8b: *Feeling isolated, lonely and trapped*

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
34	100%	4	100%	19	100%	11	100%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"He wouldn't allow me to see anyone. I had no friends. The only time I went out it was if he took me out. I was really, really lonely. I would sit and watch the clock tick, waiting for hours for him to come home."

"The abuse was constant, before the wound has healed it is opened up again. I wasn't able to heal to protect myself. And the damage goes deeper each time I felt trapped and suffocated, I locked myself in the bathroom to get away – and had panic attacks when I did. It was just a matter of time before I got to suicide – no hope, no point and no way out."

"You are trapped – if I had known I wouldn't have given him the time of day. Before you know it you're in over your head. In my case, with four children and no means of independent survival. And in any case, having left him, my daily life is still a living hell."

Table 8c: *Fearing going crazy (not sure what to believe/what is real/not trusting own judgement)*

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
34	100%	4	100%	19	100%	11	100%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"He convinced me that I had mental health problems and that if you did, then you are 'possessed by the Devil'. I was therefore a 'bad person' and 'not acceptable'."

"I ended up doubting my own thought process, my memory and my faith. He used my religion. He unpicked my identity. Even now, I doubt about who I am and what I enjoy."

"I was lost, depressed, crying all the time. I felt as if I was losing my mind."

Table 8d: *Catastrophizing and emotional dysregulation*

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
34	100%	4	100%	19	100%	11	100%

Catastrophizing is a cognitive distortion in which a negative event is experienced as a disaster (Sam, 2013). This was described to the participants in this research as: feeling that everything is going wrong when even quite a small negative thing happens (you drop something, someone fails to return your greeting or you mislay your keys or miss the bus). Catastrophizing is clearly associated with fear of pain and a range of negative feelings including rumination, anxiety, depression, self-criticism/negative self-view (Keogh & Asmundson, 2004). Catastrophizing appears to have a bi-directional relationship with PTSD (Tull, 2021; Seligman et al., 2019).

Emotional dysregulation is an emotional response which is disproportionate to the stimulus. This occurs when an individual is overwhelmed by anxiety associated with a particular emotion. We described it to the victims in this research as: having to manage your feelings because they can go (often quickly) from one extreme to another. Individuals experiencing emotional dysregulation are often not aware of the emotion covered by the anxiety. (Fredrickson et al., 2018). The degree of emotional dysregulation experienced by the victims in our research is likely to have been a function of overwhelming by fear.

Emotion dysregulation is recognised to be a core component of PTSD (Frewen et al., 2006; Etkin et al., 2007; Seligoswski et al., 2015). Frewen et al., 2006 also note that emotional dysregulation drives hypervigilance and attentional biases, enhanced startle response, hyper-arousal, numbing, irritability, heightened trauma memories, generalization of fear, and avoidance of emotional material or trauma reminders.

The symptoms of catastrophizing and emotional dysregulation, together with other circumstantial evidence, could be useful indicators to family, friends and professionals that a victim may be experiencing more abuse than she is able to disclose. However, prescribed anti-depressants mask these symptoms. A participant described this as follows:

“I have coped by being on anti-depressants for the past four years. I have been off them for one month now. The anti-depressants stop you having extreme swings in your emotions. These have come back with no medication in my system to moderate them... but I can’t be on medication all my life.”

Another significant challenge posed by PTSD in general and emotional dysregulation in particular is that individuals who experience them have difficulty with accurately assessing risk i.e., they have an impaired ability to discriminate between danger and safety. This is critical for victims trying to keep themselves and their children safe (and, again, anti-depressants are likely to exacerbate the situation).

The participants described their experience of catastrophizing and emotional dysregulation in the following ways:

“My mood was all over the place with angry outbursts and sudden bouts of crying. Colleagues were really supportive when I would suddenly start crying at work.”

“The littlest thing could send me off the rails. I would be very angry and suicidal and then very calm – I never knew when I was going to be up and down. ”

"I was depressed and crying all the time, but I was also arguing and aggressive or irritable with everyone."

"I was swinging between blowing up, having meltdowns and crying. Always feeling worthless and shamed."

"At first my feelings yo-yo-ed all over the place, but then I became just a shell, really empty, nothing. I had no energy for anger. I just felt pathetic and worthless, not worth the time or effort to help."

Table 8e: *Feeling shame*

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
33	97%	3	75%	19	100%	11	100%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"The other emotion was shame. He coerced me into doing a lot of sexual things I am ashamed of – I am a slag."

The coercion and abuse was how I ended up doing shameful things: "You feel like you can't say no." I couldn't seek help because no-one would understand the coercion and control and abuse that led up to that. There are still some things that I can only write down, I can't say it."

"I felt horrible shame from being raped. I can't be cuddled now because as soon as someone tries to put their arms around me, I get triggered into panicking and freaking out."

"The shame was awful; shame and hopelessness – me pleading with him not to rape or beat me."

Table 8f: *Feeling like a fraud*

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
34	100%	4	100%	19	100%	11	100%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"I felt like a total fraud because I had started believing that what I was getting from him was all I deserved; that I was not as good as other people and that I was not worth proper love and affection."

"Fraud – one of my sons said I was an 'impersonator'. Well, none of it was me – in the home being abused wasn't me and nor was the mask I put on to my children and outside the home. I have had two-years of therapy and my personality is just starting to come out. It has not been easy because the people closest to you have got used to manipulating you like he did."

"I was wearing a mask that everything's fine and perfect when everything was falling apart. I was falling apart."

Table 8g: *Feeling that life is unbearable; feeling that there is no hope of changing what is happening; feeling worthless and burdensome; and feeling hopeless*

Participants feelings	All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
	Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
<i>Life is unbearable</i>	33	97%	3	75%	19	100%	11	100%
<i>No hope of changing what is happening</i>	34	100%	4	100%	19	100%	11	100%
<i>Worthless</i>	34	100%	4	100%	19	100%	11	100%
<i>Burdensome</i>	33	97%	3	75%	19	100%	11	100%
<i>Hopeless</i>	34	100%	4	100%	19	100%	11	100%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"He was just using me for sex and money; but I had become completely reliant on him. I felt so worthless and such a 'shit' mum that I believed him when he said I wouldn't be able to live without him. He said he was too good for me and that I wasn't worthy to be with him; that I was 'unbearable', 'clingy' and a burden."

"I felt worthless – he gave me the silent treatment; I felt helpless and hopeless – no future – where shall I go, what shall I do? I thought about giving up."

"I felt worthless, ashamed, very scared all the time. They (him and his parents) had manipulated me into thinking that I was a burden to everyone. I really felt like I was a burden. I felt so bad I couldn't ask anyone for help."

"He wanted me to rely on him all the time. When I did I had to be grateful. But then he would hurt me again."

"You give up because any moves you make to minimise the abuse are futile – resistance from the victim just changes how he controls and abuses. Every day I had a safety plan based on what I thought he would do. None of it stopped the beating and the rape and the psychological abuse."

Participants before the abuse

Participants were asked to describe themselves before they met the abuser and 25 (74%) of them did so. Some of them also compared themselves before, meeting the abuser with the person they now experience themselves to be after the abuse.

Examples of the descriptions of the participants' personalities:

"Before I met him, I loved life. I was a happy person. I used to do good things, study, love my family and children. I wanted a future with a nice house and a supportive relationship."

"I used to be happy and confident. I was active and laughing and I had a good circle of friends who I had fun with. I was free to do anything. I had loving parents who I also could have fun with; and I had no financial worries."

"I was a fun and happy person. Before I was married, I was socialising, happy, confident, I looked after myself and I had my hair nice and wore makeup."

"I was exuberant, extrovert, the life and soul of the party. I was very honest and caring and loving. I was always wanting to help people. I was inquisitive, enthusiastic and curious – wanting to learn more and do more. I am a problem-solving person. I was ambitious."

And these descriptions of the participants' accomplishments:

"I had been working before we got married and I had been learning to drive before the wedding. I was a 'normal' young woman."

"I had a psychology Undergraduate degree and a psychology Masters degree. I was commencing a conversion course turning the Masters into a PhD."

"I owned my own city-centre flat."

"When I met him, I was doing a degree in psychology to educate myself about autism (because my three children are all on the spectrum). I wanted to be a clinical psychologist."

"I was an entrepreneur; I had set up and was running a social enterprise and I was doing community work."

"I was happy. I was a qualified psychiatric nurse earning £25k pa. I also completed a university degree."
"I got my A-levels and a job and I was applying to go to university."

"I owned my own house, had a performing and teaching career, and a wide social and professional network."

"I was much more financially successful than he was. When we met, I owned my own house, I had my own business, I had money in the bank. I was a competent and confident single mum with a child."

Examples of the participants' descriptions of how they had changed as a result of the abuse include:

"I remember being happy and carefree, a girl who didn't think twice about security (like whether a door is locked) and who's approaching me (like walking behind me in the street). Now it just takes a certain phrase, someone's appearance or expression, a location or a smell to trigger bad feelings."

"You can't go back. All I want is to feel happy again. Even with medication, I am not 'happy' like I was before all this happened."

"Before I met him, I was confident, I cared about people, I always tried to do the right thing. I was too naïve, too kind. I trusted people. I was a happy person before I met him. Now, after the physical abuse and the mental torture - I'm not the same person. I don't trust anyone anymore. I am too scared. The mental torture he put me through has scarred me for life."

"I will never be that girl I used to be – loving and free and innocent."

"I had no mental health problems, and I was able to talk without any difficulties. I used to be a first- class university student and now I am someone who can't string two words together. Now I have no job, no prospects and the conversion course has had to be postponed."

"I did not have depression until the beatings, and it got worse with the beatings when I had the baby. Now because of the beatings, I have fibromyalgia, severe asthma, arthritis and daily medication for depression. I am registered disabled and have a disabled parking badge because I can't walk far. My eldest son has depression (He is 12 years old now and always scared. He still checks to see if he is doing things right – in case he gets a beating. And my second child has autism because of the beatings while I was pregnant."

"I had lots of drive and ambition. I wanted to do things in life. I was positive. I invested in what I looked like. He got me to a point where I had no identity. Now I am having to relearn how to live again. How to care for myself and do normal things."

"I used to be such a positive person. When I did have contact with them, they said I was 'hollow' and 'empty' and 'tired'. That was from being a cheerful, positive person."

"As a result of the beatings, I am left with arthritis and serious mobility difficulties. I have had to have a walk-in shower fitted because I can't get in and out of a bath."

Findings: The participant's coping strategies

The interim impacts included the previous victims' ability to introduce coping strategies which may have been effective at mitigating the negative impact of the domestic abuse in the short term. Although, some of the victims' coping strategies were maladaptive and potentially harmful, depending on the intensity of their use. The participants were asked about how they managed their feelings (what were their ways of coping/ how they managed their feelings. Analysis of their responses is set out in Tables 9a to 9i. The difference between the participants who did not experience suicidal thoughts or attempt suicide and those who attempted suicide appears to have been influenced by:

Being able to benefit from particularly effective coping mechanisms, such as:

Religion – the proportion of participants without suicidal ideation/attempt was 50% compared to those who attempted suicide 9% (a 41-percentage point difference). Additionally helpful was the fact that participants said their religion forbade them to use alcohol and/or drugs, which research indicates are strongly predictive of suicidality.

Denial – the proportion of participants without suicidal ideation/attempt was 75% compared to those who attempted suicide 36% (a 39-percentage point difference).

Self-distraction – the proportion of participants without suicidal ideation/attempt was 75% compared to those who attempted suicide 36% (a 39-percentage point difference).

And not relying on harmful coping mechanisms, such as:

Self-harm – the proportion of participants who attempted suicide who used self-harm such as cutting to cope was 55% compared to 25% for those without suicidal ideation/attempt (a 30-percentage point difference).

Substance use – the proportion of participants who attempted suicide who used alcohol and/or drugs to cope was 50% compared to 27% for those without suicidal ideation/attempt 27% (a 23-percentage point difference).

Eating in a disordered way – the proportion of participants who attempted suicide who ate in a disordered way was 45% compared to 25% for those without suicidal ideation/attempt (a 20-percentage point difference).

Table 9a: Participants experience of avoidance/hypervigilance

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
33	97%	3	75%	19	100%	11	100%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

“Hypervigilance – it was exhausting, treading on eggshells, always watching his behaviour and aware of trying not to say the wrong thing. I would be judging his body posture and his footsteps, his expression and tenseness. Even in bed, I couldn’t sleep because he would wake in the night and attack me while I was asleep.”

“I coped at first by ‘avoiding’ – drinking and going on online dating apps to make myself feel better. Then I started ‘avoiding’ by gambling and got into a lot of debt.”

“I would sneak an online order e.g., a parcel of food; then I would have to hide the packaging in the neighbour’s bin, so that he didn’t find it and turn his anger on me.”

It took me a while to discover that the gas for heating and hot water wasn’t broken, he was just turning it off before he went out for the day. So, I would turn it on, and then turn it off again (and let the house cool down) before he got back.”

Table 9b: Participants' using religion to cope

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
12	35%	2	50%	9	47%	1	9%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"Prayer really, really helped me. Whenever I felt alone, I used to pray to comfort myself."

"Religion helped me cope. It stopped me turning to alcohol or drugs, like anti-depressants or self-harming. They are not allowed in my religion. I still pray five times a day. I work as hard as I can to be a good person."

Table 9c: Participants' finding a confidante or a service for emotional and/or practical support

Participants experience	All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
	Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
<i>Finding a confidante for emotional support</i>	20	59%	2	50%	13	68%	5	45%
<i>Finding practical help</i>	5	15%	0	0%	4	21%	1	9%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

I called the Samaritans and talked to them. When they understood what was happening, they told me to leave. With their support, I packed my bags and with help from my family and the police I left."

"I survived because I was making secret calls to a domestic abuse service for support."

"I turned to social media to have online friends."

"There was a teacher who I could talk to, she was really understanding and one day when it had been really bad, the school called the police and they took the children to a family friend (the only person I knew who didn't believe him). The school saved me."

"One of things that really helped was talking to a friend who I managed to keep up a sneaky relationship with. In the end she rescued me – calling the police and coming to fetch me in her car."

Table 9d: Participants' using self-distraction and/or denial to cope

Participants experience	All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
	Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
<i>Self distraction</i>	19	56%	3	75%	12	63%	4	36%
<i>Denial</i>	18	53%	3	75%	11	58%	4	36%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"I used self-distraction – don't let your mind be unoccupied and have space to think about what was really happening. I did it with knitting. I typed at work and then I would come home and knit all evening till I went to bed. Knitting stops your mind thinking. It was so bad that I was diagnosed with repetitive strain injury."

"I love makeup. He didn't like me doing it, so I started doing it in secret. I would plan and start taking it off my face an hour before he was due home."

"I coped by being in denial – blanking feelings about not wanting to be here (in the world). It is a toxic coping strategy, I came very, very close to suicide. I stood in the kitchen with a knife deciding to cut my throat."

Table 9e: Participants' venting negative emotion in their efforts to cope

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
10	29%	0	0%	7	37%	3	27%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"I kept having angry outbursts. I went to his work and in the carpark, I told him that I was going to tell everyone that he was a drug addict. He pushed me across the car and started strangling me, but some men came and stopped him."

"My feelings were all over the place. I was swinging between blowing up, having meltdowns and crying."

Table 9f: Participants' using drugs and/or alcohol to cope

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
8	24%	2	50%	3	16%	3	27%

* Although this is a high percentage which could suggest substance use is effective in avoiding suicidal thoughts - relying on this coping strategy is harmful in other ways.

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"I was drinking a lot. I used alcohol to cope, to numb it all. Now that I don't drink, I get flash backs and tiggers and every day I fight with my mind."

"Alcohol. I drank too much. I have since stopped wanting to drink more than the occasional glass of wine."

Table 9g: Participants' coping through behavioural disengagement (including from themselves)

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
28	82%	3	75%	17	89%	8	73%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"In the end I could not think straight. I could not function. I was just sitting, with a blank face, not eating, just sitting. He had got me to a point where I didn't trust anyone, so I couldn't get help."

"At first, I was shocked and then I became an emotional wreck. Then I just had 'no feelings' about it all, the abuse and about him and my life. It goes from bottling it up, then all the feelings, then just a monotone...."

"I was not caring for myself and had been reduced to almost no mental capacity by him and the hospital released me back into the house to be abused. I was suicidal."

"I was so scared of him that I 'disappeared as a person'. Me as a person no longer existed. The real me? I didn't know her; who I was, what I wanted."

Table 9h: Participants' coping by blaming themselves

All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
26	76%	2	50%	17	89%	7	64%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"Self-blame – at first, I thought if I could just be a better wife and mother it would be alright. Then I realised there was nothing I could do. Then I blamed myself for getting involved with him but by then it was too late, I had four children and no money, I couldn't get out."

"I told people, I told his parents; no-one did anything. You start questioning yourself when everyone turns their back on you. You think it must be you. So, yes, I blamed myself."

"I blamed myself and he and his friends blamed me, saying that I led him on. They called me 'psycho'. It was all my fault, I'm bad."

Table 9i: Participants' coping through self-harm and/or eating in a disordered way

Participants experience	All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
	Total (n=34)	%	Total (n=4)	%	Total (n=19)	%	Total (n=11)	%
Self harm	10	29%	1	25%	3	16%	6	55%
Eating in a disordered way	11	32%	1	25%	5	26%	5	45%

Participants described these scenarios in the following ways:

"I also began over-eating. I used to be overweight years before, and started putting that weight back on again. I remember the same thing happening when I was a child and was trying to cope with my parents' domestic abuse."

"He would stand over me (for everything and) when I was cooking, criticising me and telling me I was useless. I got so stressed cooking that I couldn't eat in front of people. So, he said I had an eating disorder."

"I self-harmed after being abused as a child, but I had stopped for ten years before I met him. Then, when he started abusing me, I started again – cutting."

Findings: The participant's coping strategies

Participants were asked about the contact they had with services during the time that they were in the abusive relationship. They provided information about their contact with health services, the police, children's social care, schools, housing, immigration services, the Family courts and voluntary and community sector services e.g., community and residential (Refuge) domestic abuse services and the Samaritans. They also described the support or lack of support, they received from their colleagues, employers, peers at university and other groups. Several victims described how services saved them, e.g:

“The paramedic examined me and then he said he couldn’t feel the baby and I would have to go to hospital for a scan to check if it was okay. When I was in the ambulance (and he was following in his car), the paramedic told me the baby was fine, they just wanted to talk to me without him there. When we got to the hospital, they took me into a room alone and they gave me toast and tea and let me call my parents.”

And also, where services exacerbated the situation:

“The friend called an ambulance and the police, and they got me to hospital. The mental health team and a hospital social worker were there, and she said: ‘you’re not going to have your children now.’ I was in a bad mental state, so I went back to my hospital room and tried to hang myself.”

In this report we have focused on the feedback about contact with health services and the police.

Participants' contact with the police

In twenty-two cases the police aware of domestic abuse during the relationship. Information about police involvement emerged through the victims’ narratives and is explored in the discussion below Table 10. In addition to exploring why there was no police contact, the table captures three of the emerging themes as key data-points. The first was whether the previous victim felt that the police helped her whilst she was in the abusive relationship. The second was whether the police believed the perpetrator and acted against the victim (distinct from not acting to support the victim). The third key data-point was whether the police helped the victim to leave the relationship.

Table 10: Participant contact with the police

Participants experience	All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
	Row a n=34 Rows b-f n=22	%	Row a n=4 Rows b-f n=1	%	Row a n=19 Rows b-f n=13	%	Row a n=11 Rows b-f n=8	%
Victim was in contact with police during the relationship	22	65%	1	25%	13	68%	8	73%
No because victim didn't realise it was abuse	2	6%	1	25%	1	5%	0	0%
No because the victim did not think police would help	11	32%	3	75%	5	26%	3	27%
Police helped (in the cases they knew about)	10	45%	1	100%	6	46%	3	38%
Police believed the abuser and acted against the victim	4	18%	0	0%	2	13%	2	25%

Participants experience	All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
	Row a n=34 Rows b-f n=22	%	Row a n=4 Rows b-f n=1	%	Row a n=19 Rows b-f n=13	%	Row a n=11 Rows b-f n=8	%
<i>Police believed the abuser and acted against the victim</i>	4	18%	0	0%	2	13%	2	25%
Police helped the survivor leave (in the cases they knew about)	8	36%	1	100%	4	31%	3	38%

Almost three quarters (73%) of the participants who were in contact with the police attempted suicide, compared with just over two-thirds (68%) of the victims with suicidal ideation. Only a quarter (25%) of the participants who did not have suicidal thoughts or attempt suicide were in contact with the police. The main reason given for not contacting the police was the participants' belief that the police would not help. Less than half (46%) of the participants with suicidal ideation and fewer than that (38%) of the victims who attempted suicide said that the police helped them whilst they were in the relationship. Included in these two groups were the approximately one third of participants [who were in contact with the police] who said that the police had helped them leave the relationship.

Of the 22 participants who received help to leave the abusive relationship, the police were involved in eight cases. In three of the eight cases the police acted on their own and in the other five cases the police acted in conjunction with others: the participants' parents, teenage daughter, sister and children's social care. In the other 14 of the 22 cases the participants received help from: one (usually their mother) or both of their parents, their teenage daughters, their sisters, friends and colleagues (work and fellow mature students), Women's Aid/Refuge, health professionals such as, a midwife, the domestic abuse midwives and a health visitor; the Samaritans.

Fourteen of the participants did not mention receiving help to leave in their description of separating from the perpetrator of the abuse.

Participants' contact with the police: discussion

Seven themes or issues emerged from the participants' narratives in relation to the contact they could have had or did have with the police. Six of the themes highlight concerns or learning opportunities in police practice and one of the themes recognizes good practice. These were:

Never being in a position to call the police. Participants described this scenario in the following ways:

"I was alone in the house and isolated from anyone outside the house. At times I thought about suicide. I thought no-one cares, I can't get help from anyone. I would not have been able to call the police because I was never allowed to talk on the phone without being listened to."

Not believing that the police would help if she did contact them. Participants described this scenario in the following ways:

"I didn't call the police because I didn't want to make a scene. What would they do anyway? It was always my word against his."

"The police are the last resort. He started beating me and I ran from our flat to my friend's house, but he followed and punched and kicked me till I was unconscious. My son was screaming 'Stop it! Leave her alone!'. He was distraught. It is what prompted me to finally call the police."

The police lacking domestic abuse knowledge (including knowledge about how domestic abuse manifests in different cultural contexts), lacking empathy or being overtly hostile to victim. The participants described this scenario in the following ways:

"I dialled 999 but he made me hang up. Three days later two policewomen visited. I couldn't tell them what was going on – too scared. They referred the incident to the Health Visitor. She also didn't see what was going on. None of the professionals understand how helpless the victim is. They are the only ones who can act – but they haven't got a clue!"

"The police ask what's going on but I would never have spoken out, I would have denied it, because of his threats to kill me if I did. In any case the services ask questions too late when the control is already established."

The police 'not doing anything' to help the victim. The participants described this scenario in the following ways:

"I went to the police repeatedly about the stalking but they didn't do anything. Examples include: He would drive past our house and sit outside in the driveway in someone else's car at night
He would drive past me on my way to work
He was contacting me on social media, so I blocked him; he created an Instagram account just to get contact with me.
Even now, because you can't block people on Gmail, his emails come into my Junk folder and I have to delete them
He contacted people who know me to get them to contact me for him
I discovered that there were some people amongst my Facebook contacts who were keeping him informed, so I had to delete all my Facebook friends
He had florists deliver flowers to me at work
He put Post-it notes on lampposts where I would see them on my way to work – this was scary because he would have to be there in person at the same time as me in order to get the Post-its to stick to the posts."

I went to the police each time, but they did nothing. I feared for my life, I was sure that I was going to end up dead, kidnapped or acid attacked. I had been told that he would get 'three strikes and then out' i.e., he would get two warnings and then the police would arrest him. So after several reports my mother attended the police station with me. The police didn't take me seriously until she came to the police station with me. On that occasion the police officer left the room to look at what they had on record about him stalking me. It turned out no-one had spoken to him when I had reported the stalking incidents, so he had not had any warnings. "Nothing – I had a horrible sinking feeling – we were back to the start. I felt hopeless."

"I called the police after a bad assault, but all they did was a risk assessment. They asked if he tried to kill me and when I said no, they said I was not 'at risk'. I wanted them to put a Non-molestation Order on him without me because I was too scared."

"When I did call the police they said it was out of the time limit. I didn't know there was a time limit. Women should be told to register the case. At the time we are just thinking about keeping ourselves safe. Afterwards I had been recovering, to feel strong enough to call the police. It all takes energy." "He took the blind cord and strangled/hung me but my daughter came in and I ended up in Intensive Care. Afterwards I learned that the police came and left because I was unconscious – but they never came back for a statement and didn't ask my daughter for a statement."

"I called the police when he lost his temper and assaulted my son. It was witnessed by the other children. I wanted to press charges. The police NFA'd it. That was the last time I called the police."

"There was a teacher who I could talk to, she was really understanding and one day I told her everything. The school advised me to install hidden wi-fi cameras in the house. I put them in the three places where he usually abused me -the bedroom, the living room and the kitchen. The police believed him. It was only when the school helped me and called the police and they saw the evidence on the videos that they believed me."

"I didn't report the rapes till after we separated (because I was too scared). The police would not act on it saying it was 'revenge reporting' because he took my child."

"Telling the police doesn't make you safe. They do very little. Since we separated, he has breached Protective Orders 33 times. My case has been to MARAC18 twice and I have been supported by a police cyber team; but nothing has stopped him."

The police believing the perpetrator rather than the victim. Participants described this scenario in the following ways:

"The day I left him, he gave me a really bad beating and then he put a kitchen knife to my throat. I managed to dial 999 and he let go when he realised the police were coming. These men are cold and calculating. One minute he was raging and 'out of control' beating me and threatening to kill me with the knife at my throat, then when he realised the police were on their way, he stopped immediately. He said to me: 'You watch what's going to happen to you now!'. Then he went and put the knife back in the kitchen drawer, went upstairs and tidied himself up; then he went outside for a cigarette. When the police arrived, he was cool and in control and saying that I was hysterical and crazy. He was a drug addict and a control freak, but all the police saw was a smart, polite accountant."

"He beat me up and raped me; he left after the birth of our baby. Then, seven months later, he came back and started controlling me. He made threats about taking the baby, saying: 'I don't want you, I just want the baby.' We had a blazing row and I lost it and threatened him with physical violence. He called the police and they charged me with 'malicious communication'. I had to pay the Court costs and I was given 18 months' probation."

Poor management of intelligence by the police (not letting the victim know how dangerous the perpetrator was/not recording the incidents – necessary in the Family Court). Participants described this scenario in the following ways:

As the police had not kept records of when he was stalking me, I couldn't get a restraining order. I didn't have the energy to try to build up another case to get one."

"It's not until you are in court (because he takes you to court in a fight to control you through the children) that you learn that children's social care rely on the police to provide the evidence of domestic abuse reports and call outs needed to evidence risk of harm to the children. In my case the police had not recorded the reports, so no evidence is taken to mean no risk of harm."

Instances where the police helped the victims – for which the victims were extremely grateful. Participants described this scenario in the following ways:

"My parents and family said that I should go back to him. I went back. He came into the room and said: 'Watch what I do to you.' Then he grabbed me by my hair and started hitting me. I rang the police. They came in 10 minutes and I told them everything. The police got me into a hotel for the night."

"The police were very good. They were very nice when I made a statement and they kept calling afterwards to see if he had contacted me."

"My body and face were bruised and people at university noticed and called the police. The police contacted me, but I said if he finds out that I am talking to you he will kill me. So, the police came in plain clothes and when he was away from the house. They said that they would wait for me to decide what to do, meanwhile they would record everything so that when I did want to leave him, it would ensure that I would get the baby."

"I called my father for help to leave. Then his mother called all his extended family to the house. They all had a go at me. They locked me in the house and took the baby. My father called the police who came. They locked the police in the house too, but the police made them give my son back to me. Five days later his family came to kidnap my son. They attacked my father and injured him. The police came and got rid of them."

"When he got me arrested, the desk sergeant talked to me and I told him everything. He said tell the whole story. But the solicitor said to go 'no comment' so that's what I did. I wish I had told the whole story. I didn't really understand that the controlling was abuse. I cried with relief when I discovered it was abuse. I had been feeling so worthless, hopeless and a failure."

Victims' contact with health services

Twenty-eight of the participants gave birth during the relationship and accordingly, were in contact with maternity services. Information about health service involvement emerged through the participants' narratives and is explored in the discussion below Table 11. The table captures two of the emerging themes as key data-points. The first was the diagnosis of post-natal depression and prescription of antidepressants and the second was mental ill health diagnoses of the victims due to the perpetrators' behaviour and influence on the health service.

Table 11: Participant contact with health services

Participants feelings	All Participants		Participants without suicidal ideation/attempt suicide		Participants with suicidal ideation only		Participants with suicidal ideation who attempted suicide	
	Total (n=34 row 1) (n=28 rows 2-4)	%	Total (n=4) (n=1 rows 2-4)	%	Total (n=19) (n=17 rows 2-4)	%	Total (n=11) (n=10 rows 2-4)	%
All Health Services								
<i>Participant was in contact with health services during the relationship</i>	28	79%	1	25%	17	89%	10	91%
Mental Health Diagnosis								
<i>Participant was diagnosed with post-natal depression</i>	10	29%	0	0%	3	16%	7	70%
<i>Participant was prescribed anti-depressants</i>	14	41%	1	25%	7	37%	7	70%
<i>Participant was diagnosed with mental ill health due to the perpetrator's behaviour and influence</i>	7	21%	0	0%	3	16%	4	40%

The difference in health service contact between the participants who did not experience suicidal thoughts or attempt suicide and those who attempted suicide was surprising:

Of the participants who attempted suicide, 91% of them had contact with health services, compared to 1% of the participants without suicidal ideation/attempt (a 90-percentage point difference).

Of the participants who attempted suicide, two-thirds (64%) were diagnosed with post-natal depression compared to 0% of the participants without suicidal ideation/attempt (a 64-percentage point difference).

Of the participants who attempted suicide, two-thirds (64%) were prescribed anti-depressants? compared to 25% of the participants without suicidal ideation/attempt (a 39-percentage point difference).

Participants diagnosed with mental ill health due to the perpetrator's behaviour and influence. The proportion of these participants who attempted suicide was 36% compared to 0% of the participants without suicidal ideation/attempt (a 36-percentage point difference).

Victims' contact with health services: discussion

Seven themes emerged from the participants' narratives in relation to the contact they had with health services. The services they described having had contact with were: their GPs, community mental health services, maternity services and a dentist. Six of the themes highlight concerns or learning opportunities in health service practice and one of the themes recognizes good practice. The themes were:

GPs not ensuring that victims were able to see the GP alone. Participants described this scenario in the following ways:

"I didn't go to the GP because my husband never let me go in alone."

"He accompanied me everywhere attending the GP with me. He was so intrusive and suffocating that once, at a hospital by the end of the appointment I was crying; and one of the nurses slipped a domestic abuse helpline leaflet into my pocket as we were leaving."

The victim being too scared to disclose the abuse to the health professional. Participants described this scenario in the following ways:

"I could not ask for help from the GP because the whole family would come with me; and they told the GP that I was a problem. My husband said: 'You're a problem. You've got a problem'. He got the GP to record that I was a problem. Even if the GP heard my story, the backlash from the family would have been too much. So, I pretended I was fine."

"When they asked about the drink and drugs I said: 'I don't think he is drinking and taking drugs'. I told them I had a cocaine and drink problem. He would kill me if I told them it was him. I hadn't got a problem but I did want to get help. They decided I was the unprotective one."

"After I had my daughter, the CPN was visiting me every day and she could tell something wasn't right. She asked but I was saying everything was fine because I was too scared of him."

The health professionals not having sufficient knowledge of domestic abuse (including knowledge about how domestic abuse manifests in different cultural contexts). Participants described this scenario in the following ways:

"I went to the GP but he didn't recognise what was going on (I couldn't be explicit). He just diagnosed post-natal depression and prescribed anti-depressants. I thought: 'I am living with a beast and I'm asking for help and all you can do is say: 'oh you need anti-depressants!'"

The health professionals (GP and mental health) accepting/not questioning the perpetrator's negative presentation of the victim. Participants described this scenario in the following ways:

"He admitted to controlling me, he said he had to do it because I had bipolar. A District nurse saw him screaming and shouting at me and pushing me in the street. The children were really traumatised by it. She reported it to the Council. They called him and he explained it all away. No-one from NHS followed it up."

"He got me diagnosed with: OCD, PTSD, emotionally unstable personality disorder and depression. OCD comes from everything being controlled e.g., you have/can only buy three things at the shop, which just the right money; you have to clean exactly how he tells you to; you always have a specific amount of time to do anything. You're always counting – minutes and pence and things. That's not OCD that's survival."

The health professionals not responding supportively to the victim's 'cry for help' or disclosure of abuse. Participants described this scenario in the following ways:

"No-one listened to me. I called the GP and social services saying: 'Help me'. But they would not believe me. They saw that he worked with children, and they regarded him as a 'trusted professional'."

"I went to see the GP who listened to my story but didn't do anything."

"I tried to raise the issue of him withholding my son's inhaler when he needed it with the GP. No success."

TGPs failing to identify depression due to abuse-related trauma and prescribing antidepressants for post-natal depression instead. Participants described this scenario in the following ways:

"Within a few months I was pregnant. That was when he started becoming controlling. He was very, very controlling around the birth. When I had my daughter, he said he didn't like girls. I was confused and exhausted. I had a baby and three autistic children all of whom had problems at school. The GP gave me anti-depressants."

"When you have a baby, they start controlling you." Health visitors see the depression, they 'diagnose' 'post-natal depression' and they medicate you. It increases his control.... I used the medication the health visitor gave me to kill myself. He came home and forced more down my throat."

"I was given anti-depressants. The GP thought it was post-natal depression (it was the abuse). The anti-depressants took me back into being suicidal. So, I stopped taking them."

"They should not 'label women'. They don't think about the fact that the anxiety could be because of him. Instead, the woman gets pathologized with post-natal depression or being 'over-anxious' or having some sort of 'personality disorder'. It's abuse!"

"He compared me with other mothers saying that they were better mothers than me. It already started in the maternity hospital. I broke down and told the midwife. The doctor said it was just post-natal depression and gave me anti-depressants."

Instances where the GP, dentist, midwife in hospital and paramedic helped the victims – for which the victims were extremely grateful. Participants described this scenario in the following ways:

"I was taken to hospital in an ambulance because I had had a panic attack from a beating. The hospital called the GP and the GP called persistently, telling me I can decide to leave him. I couldn't talk to the GP, but the GP booked an appointment for me to review how I was, ask if I was okay and offer help."

"It was the midwife who helped me. She saw that I was depressed and very stressed and self-harming. She said if I keep harming myself, I will kill the baby. She said I had to tell her what was going on. I told her: "I have no life, I want to die." and she called the hospital and the police. The hospital called in mental health people and the domestic abuse midwives. They kept me in hospital for three days and they got me into a woman's hostel; away from him (and his parents)."

"I was crying all the time. My mother-in-law said it was post-natal depression. But when I saw the midwife, she said it was coercion."

"When I was in hospital after attempting to kill myself, the midwife who delivered one of my children recognised me and helped me. She asked me what was really going on, she saved me."

Instances where health staff practice was inappropriate. Participants described this scenario in the following ways:

"When we went for a scan, the obstetrician asked if I wanted to know the sex of the baby. I said yes, but my husband said no don't tell her; and the obstetrician (who was a Jamaican man) said: 'That's right, you tell her, I can see you're a man's man'."

Devries et al. (2011), in their study of victims of domestic abuse (women), 25 – 50% of victims with suicidal thoughts in the previous month were in contact with a health care provider during that time. Stark and Flitcraft (1996) went further reporting that medical interventions for female domestic abuse victims with suicidality exacerbated the situation rather than providing relief or support for the victim. Attempted suicide was seen as a 'gesture' and two-thirds (65%) of victims sent home with no referral for help at all. Domestic abuse was not considered and instead partners and families tended to be seen as protective (Stark & Flitcraft, 1996; Devries et al., 2011).

Stark and Flitcraft also note the problems caused by prescription of anti-anxiety drugs aimed at treating presenting symptoms, rather than practitioners taking the time to explore with victims the underlying causes of their emotional and psychological distress. Espinet et al. (2019) questioned whether the high lifetime risk of suicide (78%) among drug and alcohol users (including domestic abuse victims) is due to the focus abstinence and relapse prevention, rather than on addressing psycho-social problems.

Findings: Final outcomes

Suicidal ideation, suicide attempts and cultural background

Participants were asked about whether, during the time that they were in the abusive relationship, they had thought about suicide – explained as 'not wanting to be in the world anymore'; and if so, whether they had acted on those thoughts by attempting to take their own lives. Twenty-eight / 82% of participants thought about suicide and between a third and a half (39%) of these attempted suicide. The responses are set out in Table 12.

Table 12: Participants' experience of suicidal ideation and attempts

Participant Experience	Number of Participants	Proportion of Participants
Did not think about suicide (not wanting to be in the world anymore).	4	12%
Thought about suicide with and without attempting suicide.	28	82%
Thought about suicide, but did not attempt suicide.	19	56%
Thought about and attempted suicide.	11	39%
All Participants	34	100%

We considered the findings in relation to the participants' self-reported ethnicities. As noted above this was to understand whether victims' cultural backgrounds might influence whether or not a victim might choose suicide. The analysis is set out in **Table 13**.

Table 13: Participants' ethnicities

Participant Experience	Number	Proportion of all participants	Ethnicity	Number in ethnic group	Proportion of all participants
Thought about and attempted suicide (n=11)	1	3%	British Pakistani	9	27%
	7	21%	White British	15	44%
	3	9%	Other	10	29%
Thought about suicide, but did not attempt suicide (n=19)	8	24%	British Pakistani	9	27%
	6	18%	White British	15	44%
	5	15%	Other	10	29%
Did not think about or attempt suicide (n=4)	0	0%	British Pakistani	9	27%
	2	6%	White British	15	44%
	2	6%	Other	10	29%

The number of participants who were British Pakistani was 9 / 27% of all the previous victims. They all thought about suicide, however, only one / 3% attempted suicide. The number of participants who were White British was 15 / 44% of all the previous victims. Thirteen (87%) of them thought about suicide and 47% / 7 of them attempted suicide. The number of participants who were from 'other' ethnic backgrounds was 10 / 29% of all the previous victims, 8 / 80% of them thought about suicide but only 3 / 30% attempted suicide (see Table 1 for a breakdown of the 'other' ethnicities).

Information emerged from the participants' narratives rather than being a response to a question, was that 10 / 29% of previous victims were educated to degree level. Six / 55% of these previous victims attempted suicide.

Participant experience of thoughts of suicide

Participants described thinking about suicide and attempting suicide in the following ways:

"I did think that the boys would be better off without me. But I knew what it was like when my mom tried to take her own life. So, I made no plans."

"I became suicidal when he was stalking me – because when you are in the relationship you think to yourself: 'I can potentially end this by getting out of the relationship'. But when you are being stalked and the police don't stop him, you know you can't 'get out of the world' other than by suicide."

"I assumed that the police would stop it [the stalking] – arrest him, taser him, or something. When I realised the police weren't going to do anything, I thought, 'this is never going to end'."

"I didn't attempt suicide because my religion does not allow it. I would not have done it because of my daughter."
"I attempted suicide in my first marriage because I was trapped. The control was relentless, every moment of every day. ...I swallowed hair dye. Someone got me to hospital."

"I left him once but my feelings got bad again after I had left him because the processes for getting support are so slow. I was very, very depressed. I was in a woman's hostel but there was no help. It was just dark ahead – nowhere to live, no way of earning money (pregnant and a single mother with two young children) and no friends. I was crying all the time. So, I went back to him; and I thought about ending my life."

"When he started with the 'angry voice' and body movements and slamming doors. If someone scares you this much, you just want to disappear. My hands would go cold like they had been in a freezer and my spine would start to shiver. I know he was going to hold me down (strangle or rape). And afterwards he would laugh. I thought about suicide."

"I started seriously considering suicide. I thought, they want the son without the mother I called the Samaritans and they told me to leave. So, I packed my bags (see above); with help from my family and the police I left."

"I was trapped because I had the threat of death from him. He was going to beat me to death before or later I told someone and my family were saying: 'Stay'. So, I was trapped. I had no work training and no way of getting a job. I had two children. No money. No house. I was so depressed I wanted to end my life. I attempted to kill myself twice."

"Suicide? I couldn't see any way out. I thought if I am out of the picture, maybe my children have a better chance. I hated our daughter; he was always jealous of her. With me out of the way he would not be able to blame her for taking me away from him."

"You can't breathe, you're suffocating. The controlling and the stalking suffocates you."

"I was waking up every morning feeling suicidal. you are just desperate that someone will help you. That was the light at the end of a tunnel. Near death the light wasn't there."

"My mother and sister died, I had no-one. I had no job. I had thoughts to kill myself. I still do now."

Findings: Bereaved Families

Abuse, impacts and outcomes

As part of our fieldwork for this research we were able to gather information from two families who had lost family members to suicide linked to domestic abuse. In one case the family member who died by suicide was female and subjected to honour-based violence and abuse. In the other case the other family member who died by suicide was male (and the perpetrator was a female partner). Their descriptions of the history and circumstances of the domestic abuse victims' who had died by suicide closely reflected many of the experiences described by the individual victims in this research.

The abuse

Abuse types included: severe physical abuse, including the use of weapons and attempts to kill: "He [the perpetrator] invited her to 'go for a walk' and tried to push her onto railway tracks into the path of an oncoming train." There were also threats to kill e.g., to burn the house down during the night. Both victims had injuries which required them to take time off work to recover.

Serious emotional abuse; including in particular, shame. One family described the fact that the perpetrator had spread stories about the victim in the community which were relayed back to her and which she experienced as "earth shattering" and "deeply shameful". The other family described the intense shame felt by the victim being "unable to maintain his position as both the breadwinner and solvent".

Coercion and control

In one case control was exerted through the victim's wish to avoid bringing honour-based shame on the family. In particular she was protecting her daughters from being viewed as 'unmarriageable' by their community which would have been the case if she had become a divorced mother: "It is the women who hold the honour in the community". In both cases the victim was isolated from friends, family and work colleagues. In terms of work, the female worked in the perpetrator's business and the abuse was known about but: "No-one spoke about it." In the other case the perpetrator ensured that the victim did not remain in any job long enough to develop a supportive relationship with work colleagues.

"Each time he got a new job she would find something wrong with it and he would end up leaving and finding another one – because she didn't trust what was going on at work. Over the three years he had 15 jobs."

In both cases financial control was used. In one case the perpetrator gave the victim a minimal weekly allowance. In the other case the perpetrator amassed enormous debts in the victim's name – such that in the suicide letter the victim explained that the sums involved were so large that he could not foresee ever being free of them to build a new post-separation life.

All the feelings experienced by the individual victims. In one case the family members were close enough to the victim to be able to report first-hand how she was feeling. In the other case, the victim was isolated from the family however, he left a comprehensive suicide letter which reflected the feelings experienced by the individual victims

Emotional and psychological impacts and coping strategies

Coping mechanisms: In one of the cases the victim did talk to family members and work colleagues about the abuse. The family members reported that the victim to a large extent minimized the abuse (a form of denial). They speculated that the victim had 'normalised' the abuse. In that case also, the victim turned to religion as a way of coping.

In the other case, the victim did not disclose the abuse to anyone; but left a comprehensive description of the abuse and his feelings in a suicide letter.

Support from family or services: In one case the victim's family and work colleagues knew about the abuse but did not act on this knowledge to support her. There had also been visits by the victim to her GP and police callouts to the home. There had also been contact with a psychiatrist. The family described the responses from services as follows:

GP: "She approached her GP in the month before her death. However, the GP prescribed anti-depressants. By that stage she needed more support than that to cope..."

Police: "We did not call the police because when we did so before they did not do anything helpful and them coming round made things worse." The family also said that subsequent to the victim's death it was discovered (as a result of the inquest) that the police had not recorded the call outs to the family home and in consequence there was no record of the build-up of the abuse over the years. This would have meant that even if a police officer had looked for repeated abuse in the process of assessing the seriousness of the situation, they would conclude that each incident as a 'first time' offence.

Solicitors: the family said that the victim saw two different solicitors (accompanied on each occasion by a daughter). The solicitors' descriptions of the victim's options and the steps she would need to follow to achieve them were too complex and stated in language which was too confusing for her to follow. This is likely to have been compounded by the fact that their attitude was 'condescending' and unsympathetic – one of them said: "Well, why are you still there?".

In the other case over the three years of the abusive relationship the victim's family never met the perpetrator who refused to go to any functions attended by his family and friends. She got him to stop working with his brother whom he had been working with for the previous 25 years and she stopped him seeing his children who eventually rejected him. The victim did not disclose the abuse to any family or friends and did not contact any services. His family think this reflected the high degree of shame he felt being a victim [sic] of domestic abuse.

The final outcomes

We asked the bereaved family members whether they could identify any factors which might have prompted the timing of the suicide.

The family of the male who died by suicide thought that the context for his decision was that even if he separated from her, everything he owned would be swallowed up by the debt and he could not envisage a future in which he would be clear of it. If he managed to keep a job (with no home, car etc) his earnings would all have gone to paying off the debt for years to come. However, the timing of his decision was, in the family members' view, related to rejection by his children. The family members concluded from the suicide letter that the shame of failing as a breadwinner and being a man in the relationship, is what kept him from confiding in them and seeking their help (along with fear of what she might do to him if he did make contact). They thought that, similarly, this would have prompted him to feel that he could not face his children and repair the rejection by his children.

The family of the female who died by suicide described the following incident as potentially having prompted the timing of the suicide:

The perpetrator announced his intention to divorce the victim; and in response to her 'weeping and begging him to change his mind and help reconstitute the family', he laughed and said he did not care about the family. The impact of this incident could be understood in the context of the victim having spent 25 years accepting unimaginable, all encompassing, abuse to avoid damaging the family honour and protect her husband and her children from possible ostracization as a result of divorce (by the extended family and community), only to have her efforts belittled and dismissed. Her perspective may have been that, in terms of the past: all she had achieved (the family honour) was destroyed and her efforts deemed worthless. And in terms of the future: she would be shamed and her children would suffer and her daughters potentially not be marriageable. Furthermore, due the cultural context of this catastrophe, she may have needed to seek support outside of her community but would not have felt confident that in doing so she would be understood.

This case reflected the circumstances for many of the individual victims who were South Asian. That was, that their life experience was limited to moving directly from their father's household to their husband's household, entering into the relationship without the life skills and confidence to cope on their own. Once in the relationship, the husband (often supported by his family) did not allow the victim to acquire life skills and confidence, so these victims were significantly disadvantaged in this way, over and above any other deterrents to separation such as, lack of housing or a means of supporting themselves and their children financially.

Fieldwork limitations

A key limitation for this research was the voluntary nature of fieldwork participation. This meant that we were not, within the time constraints of the project, able to engage participants who reflected the spectrum of characteristics noted in Bates et al. (2021) i.e., ethnicity, ages, pregnancy and maternity, disability, sexual orientation and gender. We also wanted to talk to equal numbers of previous victims who had experienced no suicidal ideation, those who had experienced suicidal ideation and those who had attempted suicide; or equal numbers of previous victims who had experienced forced marriage/honour-based violence. No males volunteered to participate in the fieldwork and their experience is only represented by one of the two bereaved families who described the experience of their male family member. Clearly more research is needed into the experience of males who have had thoughts of suicide or have attempted suicide which was linked to them being victims of domestic abuse.

Important for planning future research was the fact that many of the previous victim's experience of suicidal ideation only emerged as part of the previous victim's narrative in the process of reflecting on the abusive relationship and her feelings and thoughts at the time.

In relation to bereaved families, we were also constrained by the local and national lack of support organisations for families bereaved as a result of suicide linked to domestic abuse. As we did with the individual previous victims, we wanted to invite bereaved family members to volunteer via an organisation which we could rely on to support them to participate in our fieldwork. This was not possible.

We recognise that both men and women experience domestic abuse. However, we have focussed on women only, because our fieldwork participants were all female. We feel that our approach is supported by the fact that women are likely to be at risk of more serious harm than men (over 90% of victims discussed at MARAC are female (SafeLives, 2014)) and the results included in this report from other studies, are predominantly focused on women. A future direction of this research is to conduct further fieldwork with participants who identify as male.

Finally, we note, with sadness, that in seeking an understanding of what ultimately drives a domestic abuse victim to think about suicide the closest we can get to the experience is to engage with domestic abuse previous victims who have experienced a non-fatal suicide attempt.

Theoretical Framework

Drawing on the Ecological Model, first developed by Bronfenbrenner (1977), results from the fieldwork are brought together with the conceptual framework to offer a model for deeper understanding of the relationships between the initial inputs, the interim impacts and the final outcome. The following framework has been inferred from research findings and requires further validation.

The social construction of identity

As the context we are studying is one of relationship (between the victim and the abuser) we chose as our theoretical framework, a social constructionist perspective of identity or self (Burr, 2015; Gergen, 2011; Berger and Luckmann, 1966). Social constructionism holds that whilst there is an objective reality, much of how people construct and negotiate identities for themselves and others happens through their everyday social interactions. In other words, identities arise from the subjective reality created through individuals' relationships with each other. To illustrate this, we used Bronfenbrenner's bioecological approach (Bronfenbrenner, 1999, 2000, 2001; Bronfenbrenner & Evans, 2000; Bronfenbrenner & Morris, 1998, 2006). See Diagram 2 in which the core (I am) represents the individual's self-identity. The categories/concentric circles emanating outwards from the core represent the likely spheres from which an individual's relationships may be drawn. In general, the importance of the relationships diminishes towards the periphery of the set of circles. The more important the relationship, the more influence it could be expected to have in the construction (or maintenance) of the person's identity. In our view this could well be the individual's partner and children, followed by other close family members, then the extended family, their friends, colleagues from work and community; and finally, people from services such as health, the police and social care. Whilst the latter contacts may be brief and/or time limited, their influence is often heightened the individual's perception of the authority or power they wield and the fact that the relationship often occurs at times when the individual is very vulnerable.

Diagram 2: Theoretical framework: relational identity construction

On my birthday he said: 'You're looking so nice. I joked back to him, saying: 'Shame about you.' He slapped me really hard. I apologised."

"When I arrived in England he met me at the airport. I was very happy, a new bride coming to my home. We stopped on the way home to get a coffee and when we got back into the car I spilt some coffee on my dress and the car. He slapped my face."

Berger and Luckmann go on to explain that conversational apparatus both maintains and modifies reality. Items are discontinued and introduced, weakening some elements of what is being taken for granted and reinforcing others. In this way, the subjective reality of something that is never talked about becomes shaky and conversely, conversation makes real or brings into existence, items which were previously fleeting or non-existent. For the victims the positive aspects of their identities (e.g., their attractiveness, ability to make good judgements, their competence as cooks or mothers or in the workplace) were 'dropped' in this way. While their insecurities were magnified, and incompetence manufactured e.g.,

"He would criticise me all the time. Telling the children: 'Your mother can't do anything; she doesn't know anything.' But I was the one running the home, the house, looking after the children's wellbeing, schooling and happiness. I was the one worrying about money and coping with his abuse."

"I lost all my confidence and I became clingy – just like he said."

This process of using language to shift subjective reality was referred to by participants as mind games or 'gaslighting' and the examples they gave of this were remarkably similar e.g., the perpetrator would move an object in the house and then deny that it had been moved or the perpetrator would deny incidents or conversations which had taken place when the victim reminded him of them. In all instances the perpetrator followed the denials with the statement that the victim was 'crazy', e.g.,

"He manipulated my mind, turning things round e.g., he would say: 'I don't remember that; or it wasn't like that or I didn't say that...' If I asked him where he put something, he would say: 'you didn't give it to me.' It made me completely confused and I ended up not being able to trust myself."

This, together with the verbal attacks had the effect of destabilising the victim's subjective reality i.e., her confidence in herself, e.g.,

"They make you scared with the beatings, strangling and threats to kill you with knives; but then on top of that they plan to make you think you are crazy; that you are losing your mind."

Berger and Luckmann confirm that the psychological self or identity that is constructed within relationship is also vulnerable to being deconstructed [in this way] within relationship. A participant described the perpetrator's destruction of her closest relationships:

"My eldest child started talking to me in the same abusive way that he talked to me – he was damaging her relationship with me. I felt really bad about my relationship with her."

Furthermore, the more emotionally charged the relationship is (e.g., because it is with a husband or partner rather than an acquaintance) the quicker and more effective the deconstruction is likely to be (Berger and Luckmann, 1966). It can be easily seen that the deconstruction of a victim's identity can also be quicker and more effective by coercion and control. One participant described this as being quick because of fear:

"I was so scared of him that I 'disappeared as a person'. Me as a person no longer existed. The real me? I didn't know her; who I was, what I wanted." Other victims described a relatively slower process: "Who you are and what you do is your identity. He dismantled all of it – he dismantled me." and: "He got me to a point where I had no identity. I am having to relearn how to live again. How to care for myself, meet other people and do normal things."

An example of a normal thing was given by another participant who said: "It has taken me four and a half years to be able to read a book without guilt. Before I met him, I used to read voraciously."

In circumstances where the victim is engaged in a range of relationships, a relationship which unpicks or dismantles her subjective reality and self-identity can be balanced by a sufficient number or intensity of other positive relationships. These other relationships (e.g., a victim's birth family and social or work networks) can shore up or rebuild a fragile and/or crumbling subjective reality and identity. However, where the victim has limited or no access to other positive relationships (e.g., because they are being isolated by the perpetrator) the impact of a negative relationship can have serious consequences. This is illustrated by of the participants:

"Nothing I did was okay or good enough. He objected to everything I said or did or wanted. He said I was a bad influence. He isolated me from anyone outside the home and he gave me the silent treatment. I had no one to balance the negatives."

The impact of trauma

Another way individuals' subjective realities, and through them their identities, can be impacted is when their relationships are disrupted as a result of trauma. In Diagram 2 trauma experienced in adulthood is represented by the orange arrow and for the purposes of this study this is assumed to take the form of domestic abuse. A participant in our research described the impact as follows:

"You walk away from the abuse but the trauma is a monster. Your body keeps telling you not to enjoy yourself. There is a voice in your head 24 hours a day. I have nightmares. I wake up depressed. I bite my tongue and grind my teeth at night. I now have asthma."

"So many things trigger my body into fight/flight. My legs go numb and like jelly. It's like a hot air balloon going up, no amount of sandbags will get it down. I wet myself when something triggers me. Sometimes it takes three or four days to come down again."

The potential additional effect of childhood trauma being retriggered by the domestic abuse, is represented by the blue arrow in Diagram 2. A participant described is as follows:

"I had always suppressed my feelings. I was sexually abused as a little girl (9 years old). I was really scared then, and the rapes triggered it all again."

The impact of adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) is associated with heighten vulnerability for depression, PTSD, and other mental health problems (Heim & Nemeroff, 2001; Heim et al., 2000, 2002). Fuller-Thomson et al. (2016) found that the lifetime prevalence of suicide attempts among adults who had been exposed to chronic parental domestic violence during childhood was 17.3% compared to 2.3% among those without this childhood adversity. A strong relationship has also been found to exist between childhood sexual abuse and later suicidal behaviour in women (Dube et al., 2001; Fergusson et al., 2008), and child sexual abuse was found to be responsible for approximately 11% of all suicide attempts in women, in the 2004 comparative risk assessment of the global burden of disease study (Andrews et al., 2004). We note this additional vulnerability which may prompt a victim to think about suicide, as described by a participant in our research: "Looking back, I was very vulnerable when I met him, I had had all my boundaries violated and I was carrying deep shame from childhood sexual abuse."; although we do not discuss it in any more depth (as noted earlier we did not ask any questions about ACEs in our fieldwork).

To explore the impact of domestic abuse trauma on self-identity we selected one type of abuse rape. Several large-scale epidemiologic studies have emphasised the importance of cumulative adversity for increased risk of experiencing mental health problems (e.g., Breslau, Chilcoat, Kessler, & Davis, 1999; Kessler, Davis, & Kendler, 1997; Lloyd & Turner, 2003; Resnick et al., 1993). So, the actual impact will reflect the number of different abuses the victim is subjected to. The average number of abuses experienced by the victims was 17 and the average length of time over which they were repeated was 8 years (6 years for the victims who attempted suicide).

We chose sexual assault/rape for several reasons:

- Thirty-three out of the 34 of the participants in our study were raped, the majority of them repeatedly throughout the relationship.
- Rape is overlooked as a potential contributor to a victim's trauma because it is so rarely disclosed (due to fear of the perpetrator, fear of police rape investigations or of not being believed; or to feelings of shame); almost none of the participants in our research had disclosed the rape to services.
- Rape can indicate potential impacts for other abuses in as much as it involves violation of both a victim's physical and emotional/psychological integrity.

Rape can also indicate potential impacts for other abuses in so far as rape can be perpetrated with or without additional physical threats and/or injury.

We have good information about the impact of rape because it has been relatively well researched. There is a large body of research which supports our understanding that the majority of rape victims experience PTSD, clinically significant fear, panic disorder, depression, anxiety and other negative mood states (e.g., social phobias and obsessive compulsive disorder), sexual dysfunction, problems with self-esteem and problems with self-agency (the ability to control their life) and social adjustment (the ability to adapt to changes in their physical, occupational, and social environment) (Burgess & Holstrom, 1974, 1979a; Rothbaum et al., 1992; Veronen et al., 1979; Feldman-Summers et al., 1979; Kilpatrick et al., 1979a; Atkeson et al., 1982; Calhoun et al., 1982; Resick, 1986; Zepinic, 2016).

Rothbaum et al. (1992) reported that 94% of rape victims had PTSD symptoms in the aftermath of the rape²¹ and Kilpatrick et al. (1987) found that victims of repeated rape were six times more likely to have PTSD than victims of other crimes. A participants in this research described typical PTSD symptoms as follows:

"I have not managed to move on from it all. When I sit, the events come back to me, and I have flashbacks. No matter what progress I think am making, I keep relapsing into panic, crying and depression."

Kilpatrick et al. also reported that 80% of victims of repeated rape met a diagnosis for lifetime depressive disorder. Resick found that rape victims had substantial long-term problems with self-esteem. In view of the lack of respect implicit in the violation of a victim's physical and emotional and psychological integrity, it is not surprising that victims struggle with low self-esteem. Research consistently shows that this is exacerbated by self-blame by victims (Janoff-Bulman, 1979; Libow & Doty, 1979; Meyer & Taylor, 1985; Schnicke & Resick, 1990). Weissman & Paykel (1974) found that rape victims experienced problems with social adjustment at work, leisure, extended family, birth family the family unit and managing finances and social relationships. Resick et al. (1988) reported that rape victims particularly struggled with work and Kilpatrick et al. (1987) found that they were almost six times more likely to suffer from social phobias (stemming from relational distrust) than victims of other crimes. This distrust is succinctly described by Jean Améry, a Jewish refugee, of his experience of humiliation by the Gestapo (in Leask, 2013):

'What is lost is 'an element of trust in the world' and the certainty that by reason of written or unwritten social contracts the other person will spare me – more precisely stated, that he will respect my physical, and with it also my metaphysical being. The boundaries of my body are also the boundaries of myself. (p28). (Leask, 2013).

Finkelhor and Browne's (1985) traumagenic dynamics model identifies traumatic sexualization, betrayal, powerlessness, and stigmatization as the critical mechanisms that make the impact of sexual assault particularly traumatic. Hedtke et al. (2008) reported that in their research with domestic abuse victims, nearly all of the significant violence categories predictive of mental health problems included sexual assault, from which the researchers concluded that sexual assault is a particularly strong predictor of short-term and long-term psychopathology. A participant in our research described the antecedents to attempted suicide as follows:

"It was humiliation and shame because of the sex he forced on me....and terror. Going from on emotional extreme to the other. Hopeless, helpless and trapped – 'I couldn't go on'."

Becker et al. (1986) found that 37% of sexual assault victims had at least one sexual dysfunction attributable directly to the assault, compared to 17% for individuals not subjected to sexual assault. The importance of this lies in the effect of sexual dysfunction on sufferers. It includes stress and anxiety, concern about sexual performance, relationship problems, depression, guilt, self-consciousness and, for victims – intrusive thoughts and feelings related to past sexual trauma (Cleveland Clinic, 2015). Other psychological and emotional impacts rape victims have been found to struggle with include anger and hostility (related to the distrust noted above), confusion/worrying about the clarity of their own thinking this will have facilitated the 'gaslighting' the victims in our research experienced – 91% of those who attempted suicide; Table 5) and exhaustion (Kilpatrick & Veronen, 1984; Kilpatrick et al., 1987).

Many of the victims in the above research would have been living in circumstances which were at the very least neutral if not overtly supportive. The impacts for them are likely therefore to have been less negative than would be the case for the participants in our research, many of whom were experiencing repeated rapes, who were raped by their partner and who did not have a supportive home life or easy access to a network of social or work colleagues, or the ability to reach out without fear to professionals for support. Ruch et al. (1980) confirm this likelihood, reporting that women who had experienced major stressors in the year prior to being raped were most traumatised. Interestingly, Ruch et al. also found that women who had not experienced any stress were also very traumatised. This may be relevant for the participants in our study from South Asian backgrounds who described themselves as having had a protected upbringing and having moved straight from their birth family into the abusive relationship.

"Girls in British Pakistani culture are raised to get a good education but also to be married early. We were brought up really strictly. I knew a man wasn't supposed to treat a woman like this. But we are not taught about abuse. I didn't know about abuse. I knew it wasn't right, but I didn't understand what was happening."

"We women don't know how to protect ourselves. We are brought up so that we won't be able to live without a husband, a man. We have no knowledge about how to be an independent adult. So, we are very scared in the world. We are protected from society; we don't learn about society. I had no exposure to the world. This was the first man who came into my life. We won't recognise a man with a bad attitude and a plan to use you."

Wirtz and Harrell (1987) found that prior life-threatening events were associated with greater post-rape fear (e.g., see non-fatal strangulation in in sub-section 2.2.2); described by a participant as follows:

"He was very verbally abusive. He started beating me very badly almost every day. Strangling me. I thought: 'I will never see tomorrow...'. The fear was terrible."

The role of non-fatal strangulation in this is important. A victim explained it as follows: “He stabbed me six times with a bread knife, but the strangling makes you live just on your survival instinct.” Perloff (1983) looked for a link between pre-assault cognitive appraisal and post-assault trauma and found that people who believe that they control their lives and environments make the poorest adjustments to events outside of their control. This conclusion was supported showing that rape victims who appraised the situation as safe prior to the assault had greater fear and depressive reactions than women who perceived themselves to be in a dangerous situation (Scheffel & Bart, 1983; Frank & Stewart, 1984). This is relevant to the participants in our research who assumed that their husband/partner was safe.

In singling out one abuse we wanted to emphasise that each form of abuse brings a unique constellation of negative impacts. These are cumulative and the harm is accordingly heightened (Hedtke et al., 2008). Additionally – relevant to our study, in which 97% of the victims had been raped, Bichard et al. (2021), in a study of over 4,000 women, found that nearly all of the serious violence categories which predict mental health problems included sexual assault. They conclude that this would suggest that sexual assault is a particularly powerful driver of short-term and long-term psychopathology, in particular PTSD and depression. This was supported by Ellis et al. (1981), Kilpatrick et al. (1987) and Resick et al. (1988) who found that between a third and a half of rape victims had contemplated suicide (Kilpatrick et al. found this to be three times the proportion of non-crime victims) and Resick et al. reported that 17% of the rape victims in their research had attempted suicide. Also identifying the negative impact of rape, Joiner et al. (2007) and Hetke et al. (2008) concluded from their research that the combination of physical violence and physically violent sexual assault are a strong predictor of future suicide attempts.

Theoretical framework summary

We introduced the theoretical framework as a way of exploring in more detail the potential link between the abuses and the emotional and psychological impacts set out in the conceptual framework and suicide. One of the mechanisms through which the perpetrators achieve this is by systematically destabilising and disintegrating the victim’s self-identity (Zepinic, 2016) through disruption of their relationships including their relationships with themselves. The other mechanism is the perpetrators subjecting the victims to abuse in which each event creates severe trauma (the impact of which can include retriggered trauma from adverse childhood experiences). To explore this we used the example of rape, in the process highlighting the fact that rape is common (experienced by all but one of the participants in this research) and usually not disclosed by domestic abuse victims. Rape is particularly associated with short-term and long-term psychopathology e.g., PTSD; particularly when experienced in conjunction with life-threatening events such as, non-fatal strangulation; it prompts suicidal ideation and attempted suicide. The link is the dismantling of the victims’ self-identity depleting their psychological and emotional resources and increasing the chances that a victim might come to view their future, or respond to one more incident, with depressive symptoms of worthlessness (Wolford-Clevenger and Smith, 2016) – and attempt suicide. A victim described this as follows:

“They take a little bit of you away every day. They chip away at your identity every day.

“He took everything that was me away.”

The bereaved families provided examples of this – for the male victim it was recognising the enormity of the debt he was left with, together with the shame he felt at not being able to fulfil the expectations he had of himself as head of the family/breadwinner. For the female victim it was facing the perpetrator’s dismissal of family honour as irrelevant (and his destruction of it via divorce) after she had endured 25 years of severe abuse to maintain it.

The findings from the fieldwork and the development of this theoretical framework offer a deeper insight into the connection between domestic abuse and suicide. To expand on this understanding, the following quantitative analysis examines the broader context of the issue, highlighting its prevalence and complexity.

Quantitative Analysis

Overview

In this chapter we analyse a unique dataset combining police data on all incidents involving domestic abuse matched to data from coroners' offices on suicides. Suicide is mercifully rare, and this limits the number of cases in our data. Our analysis of the data is thus largely a graphical one, building understanding of the relationship between domestic abuse and suicide. Our results highlight that a) suicide is around 1.8 times as common amongst those who have been recorded by the police as the victim or perpetrator of domestic abuse than in the population as a whole; b) but that this increased risk of suicide is no greater for women than for men, even though women are the victim of abuse in many more incidents than their male equivalents; c) being involved in a greater number of domestic abuse incidents and more recently are associated with increased risk of suicide.

Data

The data are from two main sources. Firstly, we use data from West Midlands Police, for Birmingham, Coventry, and Solihull on all records that have an Offence Type of 'domestic abuse' or more recently a keyword of 'Domestic Abuse'. These data cover the period 2010-2021 and comprise around 1.9 million individual-incident pairs. That is each record is a description of a particular person involved in a given incident.

These data are matched based on full name and date of birth to data from the Birmingham and Solihull, and Coventry Coroner's offices on all deaths involving suicide. The resulting match covers 1.6 million individual incident pairs, for the period September 2014 onwards (Coventry) and August 16 onwards (Birmingham and Solihull).

An important strength of the data is that we can track an individual over time via a unique identifier. This means that, as below, we can try and understand an individual's behaviour over multiple incidents. Moreover, the fact that the WMP data cover the 4-6 years before the coroners' data means that we are potentially able to understand the consequences of sustained abuse over many years versus an individual incident.

Of course, many people who die by suicide do not do so because of domestic violence. Important for our analysis is that we can compare the rate of domestic abuse amongst those who have either perpetrated domestic abuse or have been the victim of domestic abuse (and thus who appear in the WMP data) and the population as a whole. To do this we also use data from the Coroners' offices on Suicides not linked to domestic abuse, and demographic data from the ONS on the underlying age and gender distribution of the population. We thus have two data sets the first describing the DA-population (those in the WMP data), and the second basic demographic information on all other suicides, the overall-population.

As discussed in the limitations section we are categorising individuals solely based on police reports. This means that if the police data are inaccurate about what happened at some incidents, then our results will be inaccurate. Equally, there will be events that are not reported to the police. We are not able to account for these events in our analysis. Our assumption is that at least some of the events that are not reported to the police are violent, but that the most serious ones are reported – say because medical care is necessary – and are thus in our data. This is a reasonable assumption, but it is not possible to test it.

Results

Rates of Suicide Amongst Domestic Abuse

We begin by comparing rates of suicide amongst men and women in the domestic abuse-population and the overall-population. There are a total of 22 women who died by suicide in the domestic abuse sample, and 50 men. Looking at Table 14 we can see that amongst those who die by suicide and who are either a perpetrator or victim of domestic abuse, men are much more likely to be perpetrators of domestic abuse than women. Of the 50 males who died by suicide in this group, 45 or 90% involved men as solely a suspect or both a suspect and a victim. On the other hand, in nine out of the 22 females who died by suicide they were purely a victim (on the basis of the police data). (Note that one case is missing here as there is no date of death available.)

Table 14: *Suicide by Sex and role*

Sex	Both	Suspect	Victim	Total
Female	13	0	9	22
Male	12	33	5	50
Total	25	33	14	72

This implies two basic conclusions. First, in many cases relationships are more complicated than a simple abuser-abusee pairing. Second, even allowing for that men are disproportionately likely to be the sole suspect.

To better understand the 'both' classification we defined a second variable `DiffSuspectVictim` which records the number of times more that an individual was classified by the Police as a suspect than as a victim. Thus, a repeated perpetrator who was classified as a suspect ten times, and who was considered both a victim and a suspect at one incident, would receive a score of +9. And their victim would receive a score of -9. These data are presented in Figure 3.1, limiting the x-axis to 40 in absolute value for clarity. The large spike at zero reflects two things. First, that, as above, in many cases an individual is both a suspect and a victim. Second, it reflects the fact that in most cases there are not repeated domestic violence incidents involving the same individuals.

Figure 3.1: *The Difference between the number of times an individual was classified as a suspect and a victim*

The long tail either side of zero is not immediately straightforward to interpret as large (absolute) values will reflect both that some individuals are involved in many incidents and that some individuals are almost always a victim or a suspect.

To address this, Figure 3.2 presents DiffSuspectVictim_pct, which is the DiffSuspectVictim variable divided by the total number of times an individual was classified as a suspect or victim. This variable is a measure of the extent to which an individual is a perpetrator or a victim. It is clear that the vast majority of individuals are to a greater extent either perpetrators or victims, and that there are only a small number of individuals who are perpetrators and victims in roughly equal measure. This suggests that that the 'both' classification maybe somewhat misleading. This is true both for those who die by suicide as well as the other individuals in the data.

Figure 3.2: The Difference between the number of times an individual was classified as a suspect and a victim as a percentage of the number incidents.

Figure 3.3 presents the same data as Figure 3.2, but now disaggregates by gender and focusses on those who died by suicide. We can see that distribution for women given by the red boxes is concentrated below zero on the x-axis, while that for men is conversely mostly in the positive region. This makes clear that most of the men in our data are disproportionately categorised by the police as perpetrators rather than victims.

Figure 3.3: Gender Differences in the number of times an individual was classified as a suspect and a victim as a percentage of the number incidents.

The overall conclusion from these data is thus that in the domestic abuse-population suicide is most common amongst the perpetrators of domestic abuse. As discussed below, this raises many interesting questions about mental health, domestic abuse, and suicide.

Comparison of the incidence of suicide in the domestic abuse - and overall-populations

We now analyse how the incidence of suicide in the domestic abuse-population compares to its incidence in the overall-population. Figures 3.4a and 3.4b presents the distribution of deaths by suicide by age and gender amongst the domestic abuse-population and the overall-population.

We can see that they are very similar. In both populations the rate amongst men is considerably higher than amongst women. One difference between the two is that suicide amongst older men is less common in the domestic abuse-population than it is, relatively speaking, in the overall-population. Indeed, we observe no deaths by suicide amongst men or women aged 70-80 in the domestic abuse-population.

This similarity raises two questions. First, is suicide more common in the domestic abuse-population than in general? Second, is the gender split in the domestic abuse-population different to that in the wider population?

To address the first question, we note that there are 73 deaths by suicide in the domestic abuse data, out of a total of 395,532 identified individuals. This is a rate of 0.018%. In the overall-population we observe 441 deaths by suicide, and the overall-population is around 1.299 million adults, implying a rate of 0.034%. Thus, suicide is much more common in the domestic abuse-population than it is amongst the overall-population.

To answer the second question, we compute the ratio of the share of women who have died by suicide in the domestic abuse-population to the share of women who have died by suicide in the overall population. This is $(22/73)/(104/441)=1.278$. A statistical test suggests that we cannot reject the hypothesis that the two proportions are in fact the same. This is consistent with the relatively small numbers of death by suicide making statistical analysis more difficult, and the consistency between the two populations we saw in Figures 3.4a and 3.4b.

Thus, in summary, death by suicide is much more common in the domestic abuse population but there is no statistically significant evidence that it raises the rate of deaths by suicide amongst women more than amongst men.

Figure 3.4a: Incidence of Suicide by Age and Gender: Domestic abuse-population.

Figure 3.4b: Incidence of Suicide by Age and Gender: overall-population

The Relationship Between Domestic Abuse and Suicide.

In our preceding analyses, there has been an implicit link between domestic abuse and death by suicide. In part, reflecting the conclusions of the qualitative analysis. It is beyond the scope of this report and the available data to consider the structure of any causal relationship. However, it is useful given suicide is more common in the domestic abuse-population to understand what correlations there are between the form and intensity of domestic abuse and suicide.

The WMP data contain a wide range of incidents varying from non-crime domestic abuse to murder. We now consider whether the nature of the domestic abuse is different between cases where there is a link to a subsequent suicide and those where there is not. In both cases just over half of incidents (52% and 52.7%, respectively) are categorised as 'Domestic Violence Incident - Non Crime'. Of incidents categorised as crimes around 14% involve 'Assault Occasioning ABH' and 8% 'Common Assault'. There is some difference in the remaining 25% of cases. Other common crimes include 'Malicious Wounding, Breach of Restraining Order' and 'Harassment' 'Malicious Wounding', and 'Criminal Damage to Dwelling'. Thus, it would seem that there is little difference in the types of offence associated with suicide and others.

We now consider the number and intensity of events. We note that were there to be no correlation between domestic abuse and Suicide, then we should expect there to be no pattern in when death by suicide takes place and domestic abuse incidents. In Figure 3.5 we plot the number of weeks between the last domestic abuse incident involving the Police and the date of death. We can see that broadly speaking, the risk of suicide declines the more distant in the past the last domestic abuse incident. One complication is that we should expect the number of suicides to decline over time amongst the population of those who do die by suicide, precisely because they die by suicide. But, nevertheless we interpret the sharp decline after around a year as suggestive of a correlation between domestic abuse recency and death by suicide.

Figure 3.5: *Time since last domestic abuse-incident and Suicide*

Figure 3.6: *The number of domestic abuse-incidents and Suicide*

We might also expect that a (positive) correlation between domestic abuse and Suicide would mean that there were more Police Incidents associated with individuals who subsequently died by suicide. Figure 3.6 plots the distribution of the number of incidents for individuals who did and did not subsequently die by suicide. The distributions are similar, and we should be cautious about over-interpreting small differences given the limited number of deaths by suicide. However, the data do suggest that individuals who subsequently die by suicide are involved in a greater number of incidents.

Limitations

There are several important limitations of this analysis. First, we do not observe in the data any information about the socio-economic status of individuals -- as might be revealed by their postcode, for example. Other research has shown that domestic abuse is disproportionately common in the most deprived neighbourhoods (e.g. Foureaux Koppensteiner, Matheson, Ploga, forthcoming). This is an important confound that would be valuable for future research to address.

Second, the rarity of suicide means that despite comprehensive data for a large area for several years we observe relatively few cases. This, combined with the multifactorial and idiosyncratic nature of suicide means that it is hard to learn as much from the statistical analysis as we otherwise might. It would be useful to better understand what particular crimes, and patterns over time, are associated with increased risk of suicide. To do this one could estimate a regression model in which different crimes had different impacts, and these impacts would have a declining effect on the probability of suicide over time. However, this would require data for a longer period and or a much larger area.

Third, we do not observe domestic abuse that is not reported to the police. It is possible, likely even, that the probability of domestic abuse being reported to the police depends in a complex way upon the characteristics of victims, their current mental health status, and the attitudes of their neighbours and communities. This may mean that a number of deaths by suicide we do not associate with domestic abuse are in fact related to it.

Fourth, the Coroners' and Police data have improved over time. Earlier records are of lower quality, and this may affect the analysis in terms of deaths by suicide not being matched to domestic abuse records successfully or deaths by suicide not always being accurately recorded.

Conclusions

All demographic groups in the domestic abuse population have a similarly increased risk of suicide compared to the overall-population. In the overall-population, suicide is much more common in men than women. Similarly, suicide in the domestic abuse-population is concentrated amongst men. It is important to note that while suicide is more common amongst the domestic abuse-population than in the overall-population by a factor of around 1.9, the base rate in the overall-population is very low, meaning it is still very rare in the domestic abuse-population.

This increased rate of suicide, and our finding that the number and recency of incidents are related to the chance of suicide, suggest an important link between domestic abuse and suicide. However, much is still to be learnt about the underlying causes of higher rates of suicide amongst, largely male, perpetrators of domestic abuse.

An important limitation of our study is that we are not able to consider the role of socio-economic factors which may both be a predictor of poor mental-health (Boardman et al., 2015) and associated with higher rates of domestic abuse (Foureaux Koppensteiner et al., forthcoming.) It would be worthwhile in future qualitative and quantitative research to obtain better data on both socio-economic factors, and the mental health status of victims and suspects.

Discussion

This research aimed to understand the link between a victim experiencing domestic abuse and the victim thinking about or dying by suicide. Our approach was to apply a project logic commencing with a rapid evidence review which informed a conceptual framework for organising the fieldwork investigating what the drivers of domestic abuse victim suicide might be. Then we have used a theoretical framework to explore why the drivers of victim suicide might have the impact that they do, before bringing all the information together here to consider whether we can use it to contribute to improved practice in preventing death by suicide.

A key limitation to our conclusions is the sample size for our fieldwork, however, this is mitigated by research evidence where it supports our findings. From the rapid review we understand that victims are more likely to think about death by suicide if the perpetrator has attempted to kill them or the victim had experienced an assault as life-threatening, and this was similar for the participants in our research. The literature indicates that victims are more likely to think about death by suicide if the perpetrator has subjected them to coercion and control, including in particular, financial abuse. The participants in our research who thought about death by suicide had also been subjected to coercion and control, primarily, however, by way of the perpetrator telling everyone in the participant's social network and the services, that the participants 'was crazy'; the perpetrator manipulating the participant's children and/or using the children to manipulate the participant; and/or the perpetrator abusing the children; the perpetrator subjecting the participant to reproductive coercion and abuse; and the perpetrator subjecting the participant to stalking. While other supporting research helps mitigate this limitation, careful consideration should still be given to the generalisability of these findings.

From the rapid review we understand that victims are more likely to think about death by suicide if the perpetrator has subjected them to sexual assault/rape; and also if the perpetrator had subjected them to multiple abuses, in particular physical abuse, and always including rape. All the participants in our research who experienced a non-fatal suicide attempt were subjected to sexual assault/rape. They also experienced an average of 17 different forms of abuse. The link between these abuses and suicidality is explained in the literature by the fact that they cause depression and PTSD, and are commonly experienced co-morbidly. Unfortunately, we were not in a position to administer diagnostic questionnaires to establish whether the participants in our research had depression and/or PTSD. However, there is the potential that they did have one or both because many of their descriptions include the risk factors for depression and PTSD. These were sexual assault/rape, life threatening abuse, repetition of abuse, multiple concurrent abuses, inclusion in the multiple abuses of physical and abuse and sexual assault/rape.

We were able to establish feelings states consciously experienced by participants. From the rapid review we understand that victims are more likely to die by suicide if they experience hopelessness and despair. The participants in our research similarly described feeling hopeless, feeling trapped by the perpetrator and feeling that life was unbearable with no chance of changing what was happening to them/their family – which we interpret as despair. Notably, in our research, the three participants who did not have suicidal thoughts or attempt suicide did not feel that their life was unbearable.

Research suggests that victims are more likely to attempt suicide if they experienced feelings of panic, terror, and trauma, with the latter most often stemming from childhood experiences. All the participants in our research described feeling extreme fear, which we would equate with the terms panic and terror. Unfortunately, we did not ask about prior traumatic events such as adverse experiences in childhood, nevertheless several of the participants in our research did say that they experienced childhood trauma and/or that they had experienced domestic abuse in a previous relationship.

A last feeling state identified in the research literature as influencing victims to attempt suicide if they experienced it, is burdensomeness – specifically arising from disrupted relationships with self and others. All the participants in our research who had suicidal thoughts or attempted suicide described feeling that they were a burden and several of the mothers who attempted suicide described thinking that their children would be better off without them. The participants in our research who had suicidal thoughts or attempted suicide described feeling isolated and lonely, worthless, humiliated and that they were not as good as other people thought they were (feeling like a fraud). These feeling states are all functions of, and contributors to, disruption in a victim's relationship with others and with themselves – in conjunction with the shame and somatic distress which typically follows from abusive physical trauma.

Additionally, in our research, the participants who attempted suicide appear to have been influenced by the participant's family pressuring her to stay with the perpetrator or to take him back when they knew about the abuse. Also, the participant having had one or more previous relationships in which she had experienced domestic abuse; and, critically, others not acting to help the participant when the participant knew that they had seen the signs of abuse and/or the participant had disclosed the abuse. The importance of this lay in the fact that help from outside of the abusive relationship and wider family was perceived by the participants as their last chance and when that help was not forthcoming, the participant's hope of escaping the abuse was extinguished. This seems to be critical information for services who are in contact with individuals who may be experiencing domestic abuse. In relation to services contact with the police is likely to have had a significant influence on the victims. Many more of the participants who attempted suicide were in contact with the police than participants who had suicidal ideation or no suicidal thought/did not attempt suicide; and only just over a third of the participants who attempted suicide said that the police helped them whilst they were in the relationship. Similarly, participants' contact with health services had a significant influence on the participants. Almost all of the participants who attempted suicide had contact with health services. Two-thirds were diagnosed with post-natal depression and were prescribed anti-depressants. Of the participants who were diagnosed with mental ill health due to the perpetrator's behaviour and influence, just over two-thirds attempted suicide.

In terms of the extent to which a victim's ethnicity might influence the chance that they would die by suicide - White British victims appear to be most at risk. Almost half of them experienced a non-fatal suicide attempt, compared to a third of the participants with 'other' ethnicities and only one British Pakistani participant.

In relation to whether being a mother precludes attempting suicide, this does not appear to be the case. In our research a third of participants who attempted suicide were caring for children at the time and said that they reached a point where they felt their children would be better off without them.

Finally, from the rapid review we understand that victims are more likely to die by suicide if they try to cope with the impact of the abuse through drugs and alcohol or self-harm. In our research a high proportion of the participants who attempted suicide did use drugs and alcohol and/or self-harm as a way of coping. They also coped through eating in a disordered way. From the Rapid review we understand that eating in a disordered way is linked to burdensomeness via feelings of self-hatred. Whilst not long-term solutions, there were short-term coping strategies used by the participants in our research which were positive in the sense that they were not correlated with suicidal ideation/attempts. These included a strong reliance on religion, denial of the abuse and the participant having an ability to distract herself from the abuse and abusive circumstances.

Considerations for practice

Having gathered information on the link between domestic abuse and suicide from the literature and our fieldwork, we introduced a theoretical framework to provide a model which may facilitate translating the findings into practice. This could usefully take the form of assessment of the degree to which a perpetrator has managed to dismantle a victim's identity by disrupting the relationships which support that identity. The importance of this being that it significantly raises the likelihood that a victim might begin to contemplate suicide as it depletes their psychological and emotional resources such that the victim might come to view their future, or respond to one more incident, with hopelessness – and attempt suicide. The assessment questions could directly reflect the categories in Diagram 2.

As one of the participants said:

“There is a set of behaviours which will destroy another person when aimed at them. All abusers use a mix of the same behaviours, as if they had a written down battle plan. They should be prosecuted for carrying out the destruction/attempted destruction of another person.”

As part of the assessment, and already in focus in existing assessments, would be the sexual/physical assaults and other abuses and coercions, that perpetrators subject victims to. Again with reference to Diagram 2., additional questions would need to explore with the victim childhood abuse/neglect; and previous abuse in adulthood. As noted above, the importance of both current and past adverse and traumatic experiences, is that they disrupt to the victim's relationships (including with herself) and significantly contribute to the disintegration of the victim's identity.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The research described in this report, in line with previous research, suggests that there are some strong predictors of potential death by suicide that if applied in assessments of risk have the potential to prevent future domestic abuse victim deaths by suicide. Accordingly, we make the following practice recommendations for both the police forces and health services:

1

Develop and pilot an assessment tool which aims to identify the predictors of suicide by gathering information from the victim; taking into account information outside of victims' awareness as well as information they are conscious of.

Information victims would be aware of might include

- Whether they had experienced life-threatening abuse; sexual assault/rape, coercion and control; multiple abuses and repetition of abuse
- Despair, hopelessness and burdensomeness/ isolation/self-hatred
- The fragility of self-identity (based on Diagram 2)
 - The number of relationships which have been disrupted or terminated. This should also elicit information about a victim's perceptions of/relationship with the police (and health services) and may assist in building trust; and
 - Any previous or childhood experiences which were trauma or terror-inducing, such as, some form of abuse, disaster (e.g., house fire), accident or medical procedure
- In relation to coping strategies – whether they are using self-harm and/or alcohol and drugs to cope. A challenge will be to elicit an honest answer from the victims who fear police action in response to admission of using illegal substances.

Information victims would not be aware might include their own emotional and psychological state, such as whether they have depression or PTSD. Some of this information would be available from the CORE-10 questionnaire.

2

Develop and require commissioning/delivery by police forces and health services of training to ensure that police officers and health staff can:

- Apply the newly developed assessment.
- Elicit information from victims about sexual assault/rape without raising the risk of harm for the victim (key contributors to victim silence are shame and fear of police action against the perpetrator on the basis of a rape allegation, which will both prompt retribution from the perpetrator and subject the victim to the intrusion experienced by victim-witnesses in rape cases.
- Elicit information from victims about the abuse of children in the context of support for them as the protective parent (a key contributor to victim silence is fear of being accused of not protecting the children and the children being removed by social services.
- Understand the key role services have in supporting victims' self-identity (based on Diagram 2); and can act in a supportive way regardless of the constraints they operate under in terms of organisational process and procedure.

3

Develop guidance for police forces and health services to introduce and maintain a domestic abuse victim suicide prevention/welfare pathway, with local statutory and VCS partners. The framework should contain the information in this report, and any other/updated information about how domestic abuse dismantles the victim's identity and the link with suicide translated into operational understanding and practice.

4

A small amount of additional funding is made available to explore the information collected in this research about the contact victims had with services other than the police and health services i.e., children's social care, schools, housing, immigration services, the Family courts and voluntary and community sector services (community and residential domestic abuse services and the Samaritans).

5

More, and more nuanced research is commissioned to track the trajectory from abuse to suicidality and, in the process, to differentiate suicidal ideation from suicidality. The research should incorporate evaluation of any of the above pilot activities.

6

More quantitative and qualitative research is undertaken to understand the high incidence of suicide amongst male perpetrators (and victims) of domestic violence. It would be valuable for this research to seek to understand the dynamic relationship between socio-economic status, substance abuse, domestic violence, and potential death by suicide.

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